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PERCEIVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections through AI and Virtual Experiences

D2.1 PERCEIVE Theory

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the approaches and theoretical perspective of the PERCEIVE project. It makes a first introduction on colours (Ch. 1); it describes the mechanism of colour perception (Ch. 2). It also explores how coloured collection could be communicated beyond the sight, discussing how other senses could be taken into consideration (Ch. 2.4). It introduces the concepts of care (Ch. 3), of authenticity (Ch. 4) and of civic participation (Ch. 5).

This document is setting the theoretical ground of the entire project and it will be updated with indication of how the different elements analysed in the previous chapters could be mapped in design methods and strategies used by WP4 and by WP6.

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Perceiving Coloured Collections: the PERCEIVE theory

Part 1: Preserving, Predicting, Simulating, Reconstructing Coloured Collections: an exploration of the theoretical components of the PERCEIVE Project.

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Introduction

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PERCEIVE (Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Coloured collections through artificial Intelligence and Virtual Experiences) aims at creating a **new way to perceive, preserve, curate, exhibit, understand and access** coloured Cultural Heritage collections and Digital Artworks, promoting their re-appropriation. These collections are, in fact, a priority because of their high fragility that requires shared methods to preserve and exhibit them, because of the complexity of their study and because of the significance of being able to properly communicate these to future generations. The PERCEIVE project starts from the twofold needs of better preserving and communicating coloured artworks and, at the same time, improving and speeding up scientific process results, which could be employed to maximize visitors' experience with a variety of digital-coloured collections including those for paintings, antique sculptures, tapestries and garments as well as for born digital artworks. PERCEIVE aims at advancing the digital capability of scientists and cultural institutions, through a service-based AI architecture and toolkit; and by developing a new design theory for on-site and remote VR/AR/MR experiences, based on "Care", "Accessibility" and "Authenticity" concepts, with and for the creative industries, expanding the access to Cultural Heritage and Art outside museums for a wider integration with the society.

To be able to reach these goals, the project has identified 5 reference scenarios, that are used to better focus on specific problems, needs and requirements and to better identify suitable solutions dedicated to the scientific community, citizens and creative industries.

This **first scenario** is dedicated to the problem of the **Loss of polychromy**, especially in classical sculptures. Archaeological museums, in fact, often own collections of statues and architectures that were originally coloured. Unfortunately, only tiny traces of these colours are still visible and what is left needs to be preserved carefully. Although it is complex to reconstruct their original appearance, institutions believe that it is also crucial to offer a correct understanding, training visitors' eyes to recognise those original colours, avoiding dangerous misunderstanding supporting ideologies. What matters are the shades of colours, their perception and their semantics. The reliability of digital reconstructions and the authenticity of digital experiences is crucial. Disappearing polychromy is also an amazing occasion to make visitors reflect on the diversity of these shades of colours, developing a new perception on European modern society, through these artworks. The Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN) and the Art Institute of Chicago (AIC) have extensively worked on this problem. Unfortunately, the examples of polychromy reconstruction are still very few, and this depends also on the long and costly processes required today. These reconstructive studies make use of analytical investigation results, comparisons with similar but better conserved artworks (i.e., painted mummy portraits or terracotta statues etc.) and experts knowledge on ancient techniques and materials. A good example of such a process is the study of *Treu Head* by the AIC (Verri et al. 2014) and the "MANN

IN COLOUR” project, that, since 2018, aims to identify, investigate and digitally reconstruct the ancient polychromy of one of the most important collections in the world: the Farnese collection, now extended to the Pompeian collections (i.e. the *Venus Lovatelli*, *Venus Marina*, *Venus in Bikini*). Although since today there is no a common protocol of investigations on ancient polychromy dealing also with the preservation of traces of colour, these attempts are used by the authors to develop a shared method and speed up the process thanks to image processing methods (IBM) and Machine Learning approaches (AI). The goal is to obtain, when possible, reliable reconstructions of the original polychromy and, when not enough data are at disposal, to communicate to the general public, the scientific process, behind the study of residual polychromy. The twofold goals are in fact to train the visitor’s eye to recognise the colours, improving their knowledge and understanding and, at the same time, to develop a citizen sense of care, through the strengthening of a sense of wonder for those artworks, without forgetting about the authenticity of the original collection and about the experience itself. Moreover, we believe that there is a strong need to extend civic participation, involving citizens also outside museums (home and street access), developing a new Open Museum concept (Ch. 5).

The **second scenario** faces the problem of **colour change in paintings and works on paper**. Examples of paintings of the Munch Museum Collection, such as *The Scream* (ca. 1910) (Woll.M.896) and the *Old man in Warnemünde* (Woll.M.491), show how some colours are subjected to this problem. For instance, the fading of some cadmium yellows visible in *The Scream* has been seen as a possible consequence of the interaction of the paint with moisture and/or light in combination with chlorine compounds, whereas the darkening of some areas of *The Old man in Warnemünde* is interpreted as result of causes that are still unknown (Ferrer et al. 2019), thus highlighting the many potential causes and complexity. On the other side, the reconstruction of how colours would have been originally perceived is crucial, since their appearance strongly influences our perception of the works of art. What are these colours? How were they created by the authors? What does it mean for a contemporary observer perceive their colours? The semantic of those paintings as originally conceived by artists or as they may evolve overtime would need to be better communicated to the public, letting them experience in new embodied ways, when at the museum or remotely. These are the questions that this document will try to answer. Moreover, there is a need also for curators and researchers to use “Predictive Systems” that could simulate colour modifications back and forth. These systems could be of high interest also for the citizens, who, while playing the role of scientists, could at the same time perceive the digital reconstruction as more authentic, and, ultimately, developing a sense of care for these collections. How an interactive experience could be designed in this direction needs to pass through a better understanding of the concepts of Care (Ch. 3) and Authenticity (Ch. 4).

The **third scenario** is set to face the problem of **colour fading in textiles** (dresses and tapestry). We are aware how these materials and their colours are very fragile, suffering a rapid degradation, in some cases in the turn of a decade. This is particularly true for textiles made of precious metal fibres, such as in the case of embroidery made with silver or gold. Therefore, it is highly needed to conserve and communicate these collections, being of inspiration also for the creative industries, when appropriately reconstructed. While it is clear how the scientific community and museum professionals need to better study the fading process, we need also to explore how we can digitally reconstruct their original appearance and how can we use these reconstructions in digital applications that preserve the authenticity of the original colour.

Also, historical **photo collections experience colour degradation** and this is what the **fourth scenario** will be focused on. There are two types of photos that we believe are more in danger of losing their original appearance: the *authocromes* and the *kodacolor* collections, whose colour was made with specific “lost” techniques. How can we set back the clock and digitally acquire / reconstruct them, reproducing the original colour? Most of these photos were made for personal use

and not by a professional photographer. They represent therefore personal real-life moments of the last century, costumes, traditions, architectures, that in some cases do not exist anymore. In this case, how can we reconstruct and reproduce their original colour? How can we adopt automatic AI techniques in an ethical way?

The **fifth scenario** deals with **born digital artwork**, created by the artists to be perceived by the public “virtually” (either through an AR application and through a screen), in some cases during certain times of the day (night, day, etc.) to make use of real-world blending. Preserving these works and making them accessible for a public need to consider colour rendering in combination with the physical environment. What is an authentic experience of these artworks and their designed effect?

To reach the various goals, in line with these scenarios, the authors believe it is important to set a theoretical background for the design of tools, services and experiences that could be used by scientists, curators, citizens, exhibition designers. The following chapters, therefore, set this ground on concepts such as Colour (Ch.1), Perception (Ch.2), Care (Ch.3), Authenticity (Ch.4) and Civic participation in public spaces (Ch.5). It then analyses what has been already done, in line with these concepts (Ch.6). The overall result is meant to develop design guidelines and strategies useful within the above-mentioned 5 scenarios.

1. Colour

1.1 What is Colour? A State-of-the-art Overview

Yoko Arteaga (NTNU)

1.1.1 What is Colour?

Colour is the visual perception of the electromagnetic spectrum (Figure 1). While colour is not an inherent property of objects, the object’s specific light-matter interactions such as absorption, reflection, transmission, etc. are responsible for colour perception.

In the 17th century, Newton demonstrated that when a narrow beam of sunlight passed through a prism, the white light was dispersed into a spectrum. When one of the coloured beams was passed through a second prism, the identical colour persisted, proving these beams are unique and can be used to define colour. These are known as spectral colours, as they are produced by a single wavelength. The visible spectrum ranges from 380 to 780 nanometres.

Figure 1. The electromagnetic spectrum. The visible spectrum lies between the ultraviolet and infrared sections of the spectrum, in the range of 380 to 780 nanometres. (lenalighting.com)

Different materials are coloured due to absorption and scattering of light. When light with specific spectral characteristics is incident on a material, the physical-chemical properties of the material will rule the light-matter interactions. The resulting reflected light will have a reflectance spectrum which will be perceived as the colour of the material.

1.1.2 Colour Vision

Colour vision, an aspect of visual perception, is the ability to perceive differences between visible light with different spectral characteristics. The Human Visual System (HVS) is responsible for this. When light enters the eye, it is focused on the retina. The retina is made up of a combination of photosensitive receptors called rods and cones. Cones are mostly present in the fovea, a small area at the back of the retina, and are responsible for colour vision. Humans have three types of cones which have different spectral sensitivity (Kevan and Backhaus 1998), sensitive to short (S), medium (M), and long (L) wavelengths, resulting in trichromatic colour vision (Smith and Pokorny 1975) (Figure 2). The peak response of human cone cells varies for everyone, which can result in colour vision deficiency. The visual information, called tristimulus values, is sent to the brain in the form of a response, where different processes interpret and recognise this signal as colour, described by its hue, saturation, and brightness.

Figure 2. Spectral sensitivity of the S, M and L cones.

Two-stage colour vision theory (Daw 2012) is widely used, since it is a reasonable simplification of colour vision and explains many visual phenomena such as why a colour cannot appear simultaneously red and green or blue and yellow. The first stage is a trichromatic one and the second an opponent one (Kries, 1878; Judd 1966). This has been verified experimentally by various studies (Svaetichin 1956; Hurvich and Jameson 1957).

1.1.3 Colour Specification

The colour of an object is determined by three elements: **the source of illumination, the reflection and transmission properties of the surface, and the sensitivity of the observer**. In 1931, colour specification was standardised by the CIE (Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage), named **colourimetry**. This includes a method for **colour specification, standard illuminants** and **standard observers**.

The three elements are characterised in spectral terms, throughout the visible spectrum. Illuminants are defined by their spectral power distribution, the power of the radiation incident on a surface as a function of wavelength. The reflectance of the surface is defined by the reflectance factor as a function of wavelength (transmittance factor in the case of transmissive materials). Based on experiments by Wright (1929) and Guild (1931), the CIE has defined the mean sensitivity over a population (N=17) of non-deficient observers as the CIE Standard Observer functions. For most imaging applications, the 2-degree observer is used, because it represents the foveal response of the eye. For applications in architecture and interior design, the 10-degree supplementary observer is used (Judd 1968), due to the greater sensitivity to blue in the peripheral visual field.

The colour stimulus is calculated by multiplying the Spectral Power Distribution (SPD) of the source, by the reflectance of the object, by the sensitivity of the observer at each wavelength, and integrating over the visible spectrum. The original CIE 1931 xy chromaticity diagram (Figure 3) provided a convenient way to map coloured samples relative to the 'white' light used to illuminate them. The boundary of this diagram, the spectrum locus, represents the chromaticity coordinates of monochromatic stimuli throughout the spectrum. The chromaticity diagram is not perceptually uniform due to the spectral sensitivity of the HVS. For example, significant colour differences in the green region do not represent a large perceptual colour difference.

Figure 3. CIE 1931 xy chromaticity diagram.

Since the HVS has three types of cones, colour is trichromatic. In 1976 the CIE introduced the CIELUV (or CIE1976 L^* , u^* , v^*) and CIELAB (or CIE 1976 $L^*a^*b^*$) colour spaces, to enable the representation of colour in two dimensions. The CIELAB coordinates are correlated to perceptual quantities, chroma and hue, which can be derived as polar coordinates from Cartesian coordinates a^* and b^* . Together with L^* , they form a cylindrical 3D colour space.

The CIELAB colour space also allows for the calculation of colour difference metrics which provide a quantitative measurement representative of a perceptual difference. The different metrics can be based on distance metrics in the colour space, or perceptual metrics such as the CIE DE94 (McDonald and Smith 1995) or CIE DE00 (Luo et al. 2001) which consider the non-uniformity of the colour space across perception. A colour difference of 1 DE corresponds to the just noticeable difference. Different industries and fields will set their own thresholds of acceptability.

The CIE system of colourimetry has been successful as a basis for industrial colour measurement and specification, assuming a very controlled and rather artificial scenario where an observer must perform a colour matching experiment. However, there are many limitations to this. Namely, the light source is uniform across the visual field, stimuli are stationary so temporal effects do not affect perception, the viewing geometry, including the distance and angle to the light source and observer to the sample is controlled.

To overcome these limitations, extensive colour appearance models have been developed and suggested such as the CIECAM01 (Moroney et al. 2002). Moreover, colour appearance models are evolving into image appearance models, which enable to augment traditional colour appearance with spatial vision attributes and colour difference metrics (Pointer 2006).

1.1.4 Colour Measurement

Light sources are measured using **spectroradiometers** which measure radiance as a function of wavelength.

Spectral measurements are used to acquire the colour of emitting or reflective/transmissive objects. These measurements can be done as point measurements or of a whole object using imaging modalities. Materials are coloured due to absorption and scattering. Reflectance/transmittance are measurements of the ratio of light reflecting or transmitting through a material. This is measured using **spectrophotometers**. The CIE has recommended two basic systems of geometry for the measurement of colour (CIE 2004). The first is a bidirectional geometry for reflectance measurement, which requires the sample to be illuminated at an angle of 45° from the normal and viewed in the direction normal to the surface. In the second case the sample is illuminated using an integrating sphere to obtain a diffuse reflection by avoiding the direct specular component. There are many types of materials that fail at being characterised by traditional colour measurements such as gonio-apparent colours. Gonio-apparent surfaces as for example opalescent, iridescent, colored metallic surfaces, colored glass surfaces, are those that reflect light differently depending on the incident/detection geometry and therefore present changing color through different observation angles. As the human perception of a surface appearance is related to the geometrical and spectral distribution of reflected light from the illuminated surface through vision (eye-brain system), attributes of surface aspect as gloss, transparency, roughness and color need to be quantified and properly measured. It is recommended that these materials are measured at more than one combination of viewing and illumination angles (McCamy 1996). Multiangle spectrophotometers can partly overcome this limitation (Alman 1987) by measuring reflectance at three to five fixed angles. However, some complex materials with metallic appearance such as gold leaves require more complex bidirectional measurements (Arteaga 2021).

Multi and hyper-spectral imaging obtain a 3-dimensional array which can be visualised as an image. There are different modalities of spectral image capture: snapshot, pushbroom and whiskbroom (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Different scanning modalities used for hyperspectral imaging. Snapshot scanning acquires the entire image at each spectral band. Whiskbroom acquires the entire spectra at a single pixel. Pushbroom acquires the entire spectra for a single line of pixels

1.1.5 Colour Reproduction

Different imaging systems produce different colours due to differences in cameras and lighting. Moreover, images that are not colour managed can be misinterpreted by computers. Thus, the need for accurate colour reproduction. Three goals of colour reproduction can be defined: preferred, spectral, and colorimetric.

Preferred colour reproduction has its origins in chemical photography. As colour photography evolved, consumers did not want colour-accurate recordings but rather *beautiful images which matched their memory*. This was achieved by increasing the chroma of familiar objects such as green grass and blue sky, and increasing overall lightness contrast (Newhall, Burnham, and Clark 1957; Hunt, Pitt, and Winter 1974). As digital photography evolved, image processing was used to mimic chemical photography, which still happens today.

Spectral colour reproduction has as a goal to match the spectral reflectance properties of the object. This requires multi- or hyper-spectral imaging systems. The advantages of spectral colour reproduction are that *the reproduction matches the original under any illumination condition*, when viewed by any observer.

Colorimetric colour reproduction is achieved by digital cameras. From their RGB coordinates, it is possible to match their XYZ tristimulus values, or CIELAB coordinates for a unique observer and type of lighting.

1.2 Colours in Classical Sculptures

Cristiana Barandoni (MANN), Donata Magrini (CNR ISPC)

Colour was a primary communication tool since the beginning of the humankind.

Polychromy (from the Greek: *poly* = many, and *chroma* = colour) was a regular characteristic of the sculpture of most ancient societies, from Mesopotamia, Egypt, to the Greeks, Etruscans, and Romans. The awareness about the common practice of adding colours to statues and architectural

elements emerged and this topic has been the subject of an ongoing debate among art historians since the early nineteenth century. Contrary to common belief, and what is being considered Winckelmann's classicist aesthetics, the so-called worship of whiteness, the Greeks and Romans did not leave their sculptures and buildings in their original white marble or stone state. Instead, they applied pigments to enhance and bring life to these artworks (Liverani 2014).

The use of colour in ancient art was widespread and had an important *cultural and symbolic significance*. Understanding the original polychromy of ancient statuary and architecture allows us to gain a deeper insight into the artistic intentions and cultural context of these works. Ancient Greek and Roman statues were originally painted and adorned with coloured patterns and decorations. Colours were used not only to depict realistic features but also to convey messages about divine and heroic entities. This use of colours served to create a visually appealing environment and convey social status.

Understanding the perception of colour in ancient cultures is essential for fully appreciating and interpreting these artworks. Colour had specific connotations and symbolism, which varied across different civilizations. By interpreting the original aspect of polychromed statuary, we can reconstruct the intended emotional impact and gain a more comprehensive understanding of ancient aesthetics.

Studying colour in ancient art deepens our appreciation for the artistic practices and cultural nuances embedded within these artworks. By acknowledging the presence of polychrome on ancient statuary and architecture, we can move beyond the monochromatic views that have dominated our perceptions for centuries. It adds a new layer of complexity and richness to our understanding of ancient cultures and their artistic expressions.

The understanding and the characterization of the residues of pictorial materials on ancient stone artefacts is for this reason a crucial issue and must be consciously treated. Gathering as much information as possible about the original colour is indeed extremely important, offering a new conception that takes us closer to the sculpture's original appearance. The lack of attention to this theme leads both to a significant misunderstanding of artworks and of ancient artistic culture, not only from a perceptual point of view, but also from a semantic one, since a series of meanings and significances were assigned to colouring.

A correct reading is primarily made difficult by the **small quantity and extent of surviving pigments**, due to the vicissitudes the sculptures have undergone as the exposure to the elements or burial for over two thousand years; and even if the colour in some cases survived over the centuries, it has been often extensively removed after hasty archaeological excavation, in order to reveal the Neoclassical white «pure form» of the sculpture (Oestergaard 2010). **Physical remains are often incomplete, and usually even when traces remain visible, we cannot be certain how the hues and their intensity that remains on a figure, might reflect that of the original appearance.**

An important debate around several different research questions is engaging the scientific community in the last years, and a network of scholars involved in the topic is active and meet yearly during the "[International Round Table On Polychromy In Ancient Sculpture And Architecture](#)".

The results of these debate are objects of appreciation but also of controversy, especially when shown to the public in exhibitions such as "[Gods in Colours](#)" or, more recently, "[Chroma: ancient sculpture in color](#)" at the MET in New York.

The research questions that usually follow the study and reconstruction of ancient polychromy are:

- Which painting material is used?
- What painting technique?
- Which is the sequence of applied colours?

- How were colours mixed to achieve particular effects?
- How many layers?

Preliminary evidence of original polychromy can be obtained by **autoptic observation and archaeometric essay**. High magnification images allow to map and localise on the surface the tiny residuals of polychromy, even though not any more visible to naked eyes. Scientific campaigns and integration of the results obtained by means of non-invasive and micro-invasive scientific analyses allow us to characterise raw materials (pigments and sometimes binders).

Archaeometry provides detailed and comprehensive instruments and methodologies to gather data about the materials, their composition and state of conservation in polychrome stone artworks (Aggelakopoulou 2022, Østergaard 2017, Sargent 2010, Liverani 2023, Magrini 2019, Iannaccone 2015, Kakoulli 2001, Abbe 2010). A wide range of conventional micro-invasive techniques could be applied: observations with optical and scanning electron microscope (SEM) of sample's surface or cross-sections (Sever Skapin 2007; mineralogical characterization of materials with X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Wallert 1995); compounds identification with Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and gas-chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) (Bonaduce 2008, Monico 2013, Lluveras-Tenorio 2022). Since sampling represents a permanent intervention into the original material, it is evident that non-invasive methodologies have to be preferred. Among these, imaging techniques to map the spatial distribution of colour's traces (Hain 2003, Bracci 2020, Verri 2010), UV-VIS-NIR spectroscopy (Bacci 1995), Raman spectroscopy (Cosano 2017, Perez-Rodriguez 2014), X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and MA-XRF (Karidas 2006, Brekoulaki 2019, Alfred 2017, Alfred 2018, Smilgies 2012) to identify pigments and colorants, have proven to be a valid support to avoid sampling or to drastically reduce their number. Additionally, taking measurements on the artwork can be carried out rapidly and *in situ*, facilitating the exchange between the participating scholars while the measurements are still in progress (Bracci 2020).

The reconstruction of the paint palette is also performed by the **analysis of primary and secondary sources** that talk about recipes and techniques and how pigments were prepared.

As an example, Pliny the Elder's *Naturalis Historia*, written in 77 C.E. directly discusses the tradition and history of art in Greece and Rome, focusing on materials, artist histories, wall painting techniques, and sculpture. The contribution of Pliny's monumental work as well as providing a commentary on the materials used during imperial time, also implies moral reflections on his contemporary, investigating the relationship between the viewer and the natural world; a point of particular interest in Pliny's discussion of coloured marbles is well highlighted in the discussion of the artistic role in the treatment of pigments, as we can read in book 35. The most recent critic has carefully evaluated the text, not free from incoherent digressions, but extremely important as regards the discussion of categories such as natural philosophy, the divinity of nature alongside with much more pragmatic and empirical discussions on pigments. He discusses these themes in great depth in this book, in which he frames the history of painting alongside naturalistic forays aimed at recovering the origin of some colours. In the same book we also find some well-documented insights into the use, or abuse, of metals in Greco-Roman architecture art. In parallel, of particular interest are his digressions on the theme of paintings used by ambitious politicians and conquerors as trophies. Pliny also did a thorough discussion on the treatment of pigments: thus, we know that for example red lead (*minium*), an extremely expensive red pigment, was considered sacred by the Romans who in the past used it only and exclusively on rituals, such as illuminating the face of the statue of Jupiter Optimus Maximus or still added to ointments during the celebration of some recurrences.

What do we have today? What's left? Sometimes, raw materials itself, discovered in original pots gave the evidence of the **use of selected pigments in a specific context**.

What do we know about colour application techniques? Some scholars argue for example that the surface of marble was not processed to make it rough so that it could better accept the colour (Brinkmann 2004), but we cannot accept it as a general rule; on the other hand, we can state, with sufficient certainty, that at the presence of decorative geometric motifs series of decorations were made at regular intervals, such as for example those discovered in borders or garment. Multispectral investigations have also revealed the presence of preparatory drawings or small incisions on the surface, a sort of *ante litteram* sinopia, indispensable in some circumstances to emphasise anatomical details; a particular care was due to human or god's figures, whose eyes had to be intense and penetrating so that the *sculptures seemed alive*. The painting technique could have made use of a complex combination of pigments with highlights and shadows which are difficult to find in place and retrace. Moreover, while the reconstruction of the paint palettes used in antiquity can be considered satisfactory, mainly thanks to the historical sources, a few is known about ancient painting techniques and how colours were layered, and how they might have been blended, or shaded. Moreover, while literary sources indicate that different binders were used (e.g., wax, egg), these are often hard to be analytically detected, but surely would have affected the final appearance of a work.

Ancient statues were painted by artists using a complex mixture of pigments and binders and by an artistic technique and a personal sensitivity that is impossible to reproduce today. The colour palette showed that the choice was much wider than we can think today; some argue that no space was left without colour (Brinkmann 2004). Being mostly composed of ochres, unfortunately traces are very difficult to recover since components degraded in time, until they disappeared completely.

We can make some hypotheses, although we do not have enough data to completely support them, leaving, therefore, space for debate and discussion. For instance, from our studies we can hypothesize that **colours were not, in most cases, applied in a uniform, flat manner**, as the painters were always looking for the *natural aspect* of the work: not knowing exactly what the original appearance of the works was like, how much colour was on the surface and possibly what the final finishing appeared, makes our understanding today very difficult and this is one of the reasons why today there is much discussion about the quality and finish of 1-to-1 reconstructions in resin or plaster.

Even when based on physical evidence, **it is close to impossible to recreate the ancient polychromy as it would originally have appeared** (Kiilerich 2016, 1-18) and this involves a substantial difficulty in understanding the meanings related to colours since - nonetheless important to stress - colours were part of lived life from the earliest history of mankind (Brøns 2019, 311-337).

What can we do today to try and understand the use and the final appearance of those works of art? Despite, for almost a century, the archaeological exploration of Greece and its borders has always delivered more and more evidence of a polychrome affecting all the plastic expressions of Greek art, friezes, pediments, metopes, isolated statues, groups, steles, it remains today to understand the reasons for such white resilience, against all evidence. Jockey thinks that the roots of this superiority of white could be traced in antiquity itself, when passion for the excellence of the form of the Greek masterpieces of the 5th or 4th centuries, pushed during Neoclassicism to privilege the reproduction of sculpture leading the absence of colours as normality (Jockey 2013).

The last twenty years have seen museums and scholars closely engaged in experimenting with new reconstruction techniques, thus guaranteeing a remarkable experiential database. Experiments of this kind, however, were limited to the **physical reconstruction of pictorial paintings** proposing copies of originals on which the ancient colours have been repositioned (Figure 5). This kind of reconstruction has been a real keystone in understanding the relationship between the ancient world and the visitor of museums, and recently becoming the subject of exhibitions (Brinkmann 2007, 2008).

Figure 5. Left: Detail of marble capital and finial in the form of a sphinx. Greek, Archaic period, ca. 530 B.C. H. with acroterion 56 1/8 in. (142.6 cm). Munsey Fund, 1936, 1938 (11.185d, x); Right: Reconstruction of the sphinx based on the pigments identified [Images from Met museum: <https://www.metmuseum.org/perspectives/articles/2022/8/new-research-greek-sphinx>]

However, there is not a general agreement on the 1-to-1 scale reproduction of these prototypes both for ideological reasons and for the great approximation applied, although the colours are repositioned following scientific research. Recently, attempts to reconstruct polychromy, especially in the field of statuary, have increasingly resorted to sophisticated and complex applications, tested both on individual works, groups or statues **in their original context, in most cases using AR or Projection Mapping technologies** (Figure 6). These experiments are of considerable importance since the pictorial framework of the sculpture dialogued closely with the environment within and for which it was set. Understanding the work within its architectural context is extremely difficult for us today: the use of digital technologies offers the opportunity for an untried path to take.

Figure 6. Ara Pacis in Rome. Right: 2016 projection mapping application (*I colori dell'ara pacis*); Left: 2018 immersive AR application (*Ara com'era*) (<https://www.arapacis.it/it/mostra-evento/lara-comera>)

A colour reconstruction is therefore increasingly required, especially if we move from the concept of “definitive reconstruction” to that of a “**potential appearance**”, based on sources analysis and evidence scientific support. On the other side, event leaving the idea of the whiteness of classical sculptures could lead to misunderstanding and in some cases also in supporting false dangerous ideologies, such as in the case of the “white-supremacist” propaganda, that are still using these artworks (Figure 7). From this example, it is even more evident the importance of colour.

Figure 7. A white supremacist flyer on a wall (source: Start Tribune journal on line)

To date, however, there is still not a common approach to understand the most correct method, nor we have common requirements for the scientific reliability of these reconstructions, requirements that serve to establish parameters for this experimentation. An even more difficult challenge is that of being able to combine the reconstruction with scientific research data, since a large part of the investigations that are carried out, give as their final output spectral data, which are hard to be used in three-dimensional digital reconstructions.

Examples of several statues, exhibited at the National Archaeological Museum of Naples (MANN), representing Venus, Eros and Isis, most of them of Pompeian provenience, preserve some of these coloured traces, in little portions, and could be suited for such experimentation (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Examples of Statues at MANN museum (left: 2 Venus Anadyomene; Center: Venus Lovatelli; Right: Isis)

1.3 Colours in Paintings

In the case of painting, we might assist to various problems of colour degradation, more than loss, as for classical sculptures. In this chapter, we try to summarise the attempts made to study, analyse and reconstruct their colours (1.3.1) and we underline the importance of colours in paintings from several perspective (1.3.2). We have chosen to specifically focus on Roman frescoes (such as in the case of Pompeian frescoes exhibited at MANN) and on Munch paintings (at the Munch Museum).

1.3.1 Roman Frescoes and their Colours

Cristiana Barandoni (MANN Museum), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC)

What do we know about Roman painting and how can we study and reconstruct their original colours? Although this work is not meant to provide an extensive analysis of Roman painting techniques on walls (there are several publications on this topic i.e. Ling 1991, Salvadori, Sbrolli 2021), we aim at introducing here the problem of the fragility also of these artworks by introducing the used techniques and colours.

The walls of ancient buildings during the Roman period were painted using the “fresco” technique. The paint was applied to a layer of plaster, when this was wet. All details were added after this phase, painted on partially dry plaster or on dry plaster.

As described also in Pliny (see Appendix 1), a preliminary sketch of the final composition was drawn. This was called “sinopia” and it was drawn on a layer of rough plaster, called “arriccio”. After this phase, a final layer of smooth plaster (“intonachino”) was applied. The outline of the foreseen paint was engraved in short time, into this coat of plaster; at this point, the painters could begin the work, starting from the top part of the wall. These artists were called “pictor parietarius” and their technical instruments included plumbines, punches and squares to be able to draw perfect architectures as well as precise details. All outlines were then painted. There was also the “pictor imaginarius” who would be specialised in painting the figurative scenes directly on the wall or in wooden panels. From the repetition of some pictures, scholars have understood that during Roman times there might have been “cartoons”, circulating among the artists, to enable them to copy part of compositions or/and decorative motives and, eventually, adding their variations.

Paintings could be also produced on marble surfaces and not only on walls and on wood.

Figure 9. the painters' workshop (from Donati 1998, p 105)

Regarding the type of colours, painters used, as Pliny explains (see Appendix 1), the pigment employed might have been of mineral, vegetal or animal origin. They were divided into two categories: the so-called “florid”, that were also the most expensive ones, were brighter, while the “plain” were less bright and expensive, and also more widespread. The main colours used were:

Red. Red could be obtained from hematite or from calcination of yellow ochre. Among the reds, we know that also a lead containing pigment was used, known in antiquity as “minium”, that was made from mercury sulphide, which tended to blacken from exposure to light alone or in combination with chlorine-containing compounds (Cotte 2006, Radepont et al 2015, Elert et al 2021).

Green. These colours were extracted from minerals containing celadonite or glauconite (the most precious was made from malachite).

White. White was produced from calcium carbonate.

Black. Romans used to obtain the black colours from carbon made by burning pine resing or bark or vines but also from ivory and bones.

Blue. The most used type of blue, initially produced in Egypt at Alexandria, was the so-called “Egyptian Blue” (Figure 10). It was later introduced in Italy (Campania, Pozzuoli) and, from here, it spread to Gaul. This blue was made of a mixture of sand, potassium nitrate or sodium nitrate and copper; it was burnt in a kiln, in small balls shapes that were reduced to fine powder. The most precious of these blues was *armenium* (from azurite) and *scythicum* (known as lapis lazuli).

Figure 10. Cups with Egyptian blue (Pompeii MANN inv. n. 117338) and red ochre (Pompeii MANN inv. n. 112265) (from: Salvadori, Sbroli 2021)

1.3.2 Colour Change Identification and Analysis: a State of the Art

Letizia Monico (CNR SCITEC), Irina Sandu (MUNCH), Irina Ciortan (NTNU)

Darkening, fading and yellowing often accompanied by flaking, crumbling and chalking of the paint, affect tens of thousands of paintings and works in museums, collections and archaeological sites with dramatic threats for their understanding, preservation, and management. Such irreversible colour changes are the result of transformations of the constituent materials (pigments, binding media, varnishes) of the work of art, thus depending on their chemical nature and the past conservation history of the work of art itself (e.g., storage and display conditions, restoration treatments).

Among numerous examples, the darkening of vermilion red threatens a series of 15th-16th century paintings, including those by Pieter Paul Rubens (Radepont et al. 2011; Anaf et al. 2013), as well as Pompeian wall paintings (Cotte et al. 2006; Pérez-Diez et al. 2021; Gliozzo 2021). In the latter, a change from yellow to red was also often observed in the areas where ochre pigments were used (Marcaida et al. 2019). Similar colour changes of red and ochre pigments are also visible in other Pompeian wall paintings displayed the MANN museum today (Figure 11)

Figure 11. Roman Frescos. Right: Candelabrum, in the form of a plant and ribbon from Portici, INV 9770 MANN Museum (20-10 BC); Left: Small pilaster in the shape of a griffon, with herm, INV. 9859 MANN Museum.

Others yellows of low durability are orpiment, chrome yellows and cadmium yellows. The discoloration of orpiment is present in the works of art of medieval Italian masters and Flemish and Dutch painters, such as those by Cimabue (Monico et al. 2022), Pietro Lorenzetti (Howard et al. 2023), Daniël Seghers (Vermeulen et al. 2016), Adriaen Coorte (Keune et al. 2015), and Jan Davidszoon de Heem (Broers et al. 2023). The darkening of chromate-based yellows affects, instead, artworks by George Seurat (Casadio et al. 2011), Paul Gauguin (Monico et al. 2014), and Vincent van Gogh (Monico et al. 2011; Monico et al. 2014; Monico et al. 2015; Hendriks et al. 2019), while the whitening of cadmium yellows threatens paintings by Vincent van Gogh (Van der Snickt et al. 2012), James Ensor (Van der Snickt et al. 2009), Henri Matisse (Mass et al. 2013; Pouyet et al. 2015), and Edvard Munch, (Singer et al. 2010; Monico et al. 2022) (Figure 12)

Figure 12. Discoloured areas [I] and II)] and flaked off region [III)] cadmium yellow areas of *The Scream* (ca. 1910?) from MUNCH Museum, Oslo, NO (Monico et al. 2020)

Figure 13. Fading of Prussian blue in a Danish Golden age painting, *A View from Dosseringen near the Sortedam (1838)* from Statens Museum for Kunst, Copenhagen, DK (Filtenborg et al. 2014).

Among blues, the darkening of French ultramarine, cerulean and Thénard's blues is also visible in masterpieces by Edvard Munch, (Ferrer et al. 2019), while the fading of Prussian blue was observed in a series of 18th century Danish Golden age paintings (Statens Museum for Kunst, Copenhagen) (Filtenborg et al. 2014). Here a dramatic fading of the original blue colour is visible only in the areas exposed to light, while below the frame the colour is intact (Figure 13).

Ultramarine blue paints are known for having poor drying properties in oil. Although the pigment is noted to be comparatively permanent, there have been reports of changes in colour due to instability of the pigment (Cato et al. 2016). Recent research has linked the discolouration to the degradation of the binding medium, understood to be a result of a of pigment–binder separation (Wijnberg L. 2014).

For instance, the phenomenon of blackening of deep blue paint observed in *Old Man in Warnemünde (1907)* by Edvard Munch (as shown in Figure 14) may be seen in relation to early reports on similar phenomena, dating from the period of early manufacturing of synthetic ultramarine. As synthetic ultramarine became available on the market in 1907, it was noted that the paint had issues of blackening, at the time attributed to impurities or additions of iron, lime, magnesia and potash, or to the paint being mixed with white lead (Carlyle L. 2001). The elemental distributions measured by the synchrotron radiation-based micro X-ray fluorescence investigations show that the composition of the ultramarine pigment used in *Old Man in Warnemünde* has a uniform distribution of Al, Si, S, Na across the surface, in both dark and brighter blue areas. This suggests that darkening is likely due to the organic components rather than to the pigment itself. The presence of natural wax in the paint sample is interpreted as a probable additive from the manufacturers. Such additions have been identified in ready-made paint from the period (Laar & Burnstock 1997) and have also been indicated by FT-IR analysis in ATR mode of certain paint tubes in the Munch Museum's reference collection (Ferrer et al. 2016).

Figure 14. Areas (marked in red squares) with blue (ultramarine) and red (lake) darkening in the painting *Old Man in Warnemünde* (1907) Photo @MUNCH.

Additional coloured materials that suffer from chromatic changes are specific classes of red lakes (i.e., cochineal-, alizarin- and eosin-based lakes), as found in some works of art of the American watercolorist Winslow Homer (Berrie et al. 2014), in a series of works on paper by Gauguin (Daher et al. 2018) and in several paintings by Munch (Ferrer et al. 2019) and Van Gogh (Burnstock et al. 2005; Hendriks et al. 2011; Hendriks et al. 2019; Fiedler et al. 2016; Centeno et al. 2017; Fieberg et al. 2017; Dooley et al. 2020; Pozzi et al. 2021). Certain types of organic red paint degradation on paintings by Van Gogh have been linked to paint formulations containing starch and specific types of mordant-based colourant. The degradation phenomena described in red lake paints in van Gogh's *Glass with Yellow Roses*, and *Portrait of an Old Woman* (Burnstock et al. 2005), exhibits visual surface characteristics like the red lake paint in Munch's *Old Man in Warnemünde*. The red lake in Munch's painting exhibits both pronounced cracks and spotting, in addition to browning. In the red sample from *Old Man in Warnemünde* (displayed in Figure 14), alizarin was identified as the colourant, with a possible tin/calcium-based and/or aluminium/calcium based-substrate, which might suggest a mixture of two types of red lake (Ferrer et al. 2019). The deterioration, resulting in a brown discolouration of the red lake used by Van Gogh, was connected with the inclusion of starch. The absence of starch from the sample from *Old Man in Warnemünde* and the similarities of paint deterioration merit a further investigation and comparative analysis on the uses of red lake paint by these two artists. The presence of a phosphorous compound is a topic for further investigation.

The recording/measurement, monitoring and simulation of the colour change is a broad and interdisciplinary field and addresses the scientific perspective as a way to bridge the results obtained from several imaging and data processing techniques (Deborah et al. 2017; dal Favio et al. 2020; Striova et al. 2020) to the presentation of an art collection in all its complexity, not only as a material and object-based collection, but also as a concept development tool of educational contents for the public (Sandu et al. 2015; Berns 2005). Furthermore, it challenges the way the collection is stored and presented to the public, as needs to also raise awareness around the vulnerability of such a collection and the best strategies to be implemented for mitigating the risks associated to the classical

ways of presenting it in an exhibition context (where light, RH, temperature, etc. can accelerate this change if not properly monitored and controlled).

One technique that allow the light induced colour change to be monitored is microfadeometry (MFT), by suggesting a safe threshold dose of light for the studied object (Whitmore et al. 1999). Currently there is no established protocol for MFT experiments. Thus, the measurement typically consists in irradiating a selected point on an object with a specific white light with an intensity of the order of a few mW and simultaneous registration of colour changes caused by this illumination via colorimetric measurements. The light probe is focused in a small spot (typically less than 0.6 mm diameter); it follows that on one hand the fluence of light (expressed as power/area) at the measured spot is some order of magnitudes higher than equivalent conventional lighting systems, on the other hand the area of the paintings exposed to irradiation is strongly limited. A single microfading test takes up to 10 minutes and several measurements are usually performed for selected hues present on an object. To additionally ensure that minimal damage occurs, in some cases, the experiment is terminated once a colour change reaches units of just-noticeable-differences of human perception (Ciortan et al. 2022). Work in this direction is ongoing in H2020 project “Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science” (IPERION HS: GA n. 871034), task 5.1 “Methodological and instrumental developments for preventive conservation”.

In such context, further information regarding lightfastness of certain painting materials were successfully obtained by MFT (i.e. darkening of red areas containing vermilion) (Lojewski 2020). Moreover, the portability of the microfading allows it to be carried out for different types of artworks and in different conditions, such as Spanish Levantine rock art outdoor as shown by Riutort-Mayol et al. (2019), prints, watercolours, and textile in museum environments (Beltran et al. 2019). Nonetheless, microfading only assesses the photodegradation of the materials and does not indicate the possible chemical/structural changes that might have occurred due to other aging factors. A good example in this sense is that of the cadmium yellow pigment, which fades mainly because of exposure to moisture instead of light (Monico et al. 2022). In this case, the microfading test captures a low extent of light-induced colour change, while in practice, the discolouration of the cadmium yellow paint is substantial as a result of exposure to humidity.

The microfading data may support the prediction of future colour change, which is straightforward from a mathematical perspective, as various interpolation and regression techniques can be applied. For instance, Morris (2007) created a look-up table of colour changes for increasing light dosages, based on microfading tests carried out on paint mockups. Hendriks et al. (2017) predicted the photodegradation of the red and yellow colours in **Van Gogh’s “The Bedroom”**, for a light dosage of up to 30 Mlux hr. As input, the authors used microfading data from aged mockups of red lakes and chrome yellow paints and based on these, altered the image of the painting in a commercial image editing software. In a similar way, Brokerhof et al. (2018) rendered colour changes for a collection of Dutch city maps from the 17th century in an image editing software for various levels of fading and light exposure. Riutort-Mayol et al. (2019) applied Gaussian process interpolation to extend the single-point microfading measurements to the two-dimensional surface of the artworks, and to forecast the photodegradation behaviour beyond the limited temporal dimension considered during the measurement. Ciortan et al. (2022) adopted time-series analysis to forecast the individual change of colour coordinates in the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ space, rather than the aggregate colour change, for a set of samples measured on the painting “*A Japanese Lantern*” by **Oda Krohg**.

Recently, a novel approach that allows for simulating not only the colour, but the spectral changes induced by light-exposure was proposed by Ciortan and co-workers (Ciortan et al. 2023: Part 1, Part 2). The method is based on a tensor decomposition model that, from a set of microfading measurements, disentangles in one shot the reflectances of pure pigments, their concentration, and their fading rate as a function of time. Such knowledge, combined with hyperspectral image analysis,

was then exploited to render the past and future appearance of the artwork by modulating the amount of light exposure.

It is important to mention that all colour simulations (future and past) derived from microfading and more conventional accelerated photoaging experiments are questionable with respect to the **light reciprocity principle**. The light reciprocity principle states that exposing a specimen for short periods of time under high levels of light intensity is equivalent to long exposure under low illuminations levels (Saunders 2020). Several studies (del Hoyo-Melendez et al. 2011; Liang et al. 2011) have shown that light reciprocity principle breaks down when the difference in illumination between the two scenarios is of higher than 3 orders of magnitude. This is even more relevant for microfading, for which light intensities and/or fluence values are further increased. Perhaps this is one of the reasons why **simulations of past appearance of a painting, extrapolated from microfading tests, is especially controversial** as often the full record of light conditions that the painting was exposed to (perhaps even before it became part of a museum collection) is unknown. Apart from the different levels of intensity, the light-induced change of a specimen in accelerated aging tests is influenced by the spectral distribution of the light source as earlier described (Saunders and Kirby 1994). As a rule of thumb, the change is proportional with the amount of overlap between the absorption spectrum of a material and the emission spectrum of the light. An exception to this rule is given by Prussian blue pigments and chrome yellow oil paints (Lerwill et al. 2015a; Monico et al. 2015). The inverse behaviour of Prussian blue was discovered to be related to the amount of oxygen in the environment where the photoaging experiment occurs (Lerwill et al. 2015b). In the case of chrome yellow, the sensitivity of the paint towards darkening not only after the exposure to the blue component but also to the green one of the visible light was ascribed to the presence of pentavalent chromium compounds, resulting from the thermal interaction of the original chromate-based pigment with the oil (Monico 2015).

The reconstruction of how colours would have originally been perceived is crucial, since their appearance strongly influences our perception of the work of art. Guidelines are also needed to preserve them when exhibited (a control of environmental conditions and lighting is fundamental). In such context, through studies of micro-samples from artworks, laboratory paint mock-ups and direct non-invasive examinations of painted surfaces, a large quantity of data has been acquired in the last two decades from the above-mentioned case studies, thus helping to unveil how the constituent materials of the paint and environmental factors may affect the overall colour change phenomena. In the case of chrome yellows and cadmium yellows, for example, analytical investigations have contributed to help Museums to optimize the long-term conservation condition of some iconic paintings, such as the *Sunflowers* by Van Gogh (version of the Van Gogh Museum, Amsterdam) (Hendriks 2019) and *The Scream* (ca. 1910) by Munch (version of the MUNCH museum, Oslo) (Monico et al. 2020).

In addition, experimental datasets have contributed to develop first models for the virtual reconstruction of the original colour scheme of the artwork intended by the painter. In such context, several projects or research groups involved in activities related to the digital colour reconstruction.

A pioneering work on paintings by Seurat and Van Gogh was conducted by Berns, Pozzi and co-workers (Berns et al. 2006; Berns et al. 2019; Pozzi et al. 2021) by following a hybrid strategy that combines visual evaluation of the painting, pigments identification in micro-samples using different analytical methods (e.g., infrared and X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy; gas chromatography-mass spectrometry; scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy; Raman spectroscopy), single-point reflectance visible spectroscopy measurements acquired across the painting surface, definition of the original optical properties of the painting via comparison with data obtained from paint reconstructions, colour-managed RGB imaging and image adjustments with dedicated photo-editing software.

Paint reconstructions of Van Gogh's palette was a significant component of REVIGO (Reassessing Vincent van Gogh's colours), a project devoted to study the colour changes in Van Gogh paintings and drawings and sponsored by The Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research. (<https://www.vangoghmuseum.nl/en/about/knowledge-and-research/completed-research-projects/revigo/research-results-revigo-paintings>). The key technologies for REVIGO were hyperspectral visible spectrum imaging and macro XRF scanning mapping methods, as well as machine-learning techniques (Geldof et al. 2018; Kirchner et al. 2018: Part 1, Part 2, Part 3; Kirchner et al. 2019). The optical database resulting from the paint reconstructions has given an important contribution toward understanding Van Gogh's working method and improvements in digital colour reconstruction methodologies.

The application of machine learning techniques for processing and modelling large spectral imaging datasets has drastically expanded over the last 5 years, by permitting to perform advanced mapping of artistic painting materials and to identify pure and mixed pigments via application of spectral data obtained from artistic materials (Chen et al. 2022; Vermeulen et al. 2022; Xu et al. 2022; Liu et al. 2023).

To date, however, there is still no standard method that allow for a reliable virtual colour restoration or colour change prediction of an object to be performed. Deep knowledge from the study of laboratory samples and paintings to understand how the paint composition and environmental factors influence the extent of colour changes is still missing and further experiments are required.

PERCEIVE, by applying digital and machine learning-based methods to large experimental datasets from discoloured laboratory samples, Pompeian Roman wall paintings of MANN and paintings by Munch of the MUNCH Museum, will develop a "Predictive System". It will use the analysis of colour change during the time (from the past to the present) and will give the possibility to "play forward the clock" to see how the artwork would look in a span of time if no specific preventive conservation measures are put in place. Such system will support conservators but also will be exploited for realizing an interactive experience for the visitors, who could play the role of scientists (by interacting for instance with parameters in a sort of console-like or chemist-table interface) and see the results generated by their behaviours or choices.

1.3.3 The importance and symbolisms of colours in painted artworks: a focus on Munch

Irina Sandu (MUNCH Museum)

The use, relevance and symbolisms of colours in ancient and modern paintings is as broad and complex as human history itself. Exact same colour used by different artists in different paintings can express divinity, wealth, or the artist's innermost feelings. The raw pigments used in the manufacture of the paint give clues on the economic and political contexts, encompassing the history of trade, exploration and exploitation of certain populations. The understanding of a colour is tied to a particular context (cultural, social, religious etc.), so for example we see reds of the past differently than those who saw them first (Art and the Cities 2022).

Since the beginning of human history people have wanted to communicate and render the world around them using colour, trying to reproduce it in lasting material forms for this purpose. The oldest pigment, a red colour in the powdered form of iron oxide (known as **red ochre**), has been found in **prehistorical cave paintings** and burial sites around the world. Since then, **naturally originated colours** – from minerals, stones, shellfish, clay, plants and insects – have been prepared through a process of drying, grinding and mixing with a binding agent to produce a substance that can be applied to walls, panels or canvases in the form of malleable, thin or thick paint.

For the Western world, trade relations and colonial expansion introduced new and exotic pigments. Many of them were expensive (for example the lapis lazuli powders brought from Afghanistan or other far-away places) and so their use in a work of art could also reflect the wealth and power of the place or person who had commissioned it.

The industrial revolutions in manufacturing and transportation that characterized the birth of the modern world left their mark on the invention of **industrially produced pigments**. The modern artists whose father is considered Edvard Munch were eager to experience with new synthetic colours also displaying novel properties that would allow a longer elaboration of the paint on canvas or other supports.

New forms of art – photography, cinema, television, computer science, and the Internet have further expanded the spectrum of colours present in our daily lives and available to our imagination. Because colour is a mirror of how a society sees itself, through it we can trace a path from the distant past to the living present.

And ultimately even the colours themselves are not quite what they used to be, as the chemical transformation of the paint over time, and the altered environments and lighting in which they are seen, alter what we see. The relationship with colours is ever evolving, our experience of works of art changes accordingly. **Learning what a colour meant to the artist who used it transforms our understanding and perception of both colour and the artwork** (Art and the Cities 2022).

Colour is one of the seven elements that are important for art representations in different techniques and using different materials: *colour, value, texture, space, line, form, and shape*. As seen in Ch. 1.1, its main characteristics are *hue, saturation (chroma), and brightness (lightness)*.

The perception of colour is a subjective phenomenon and is also influenced by social and cultural norms. Scientific and theoretical investigations into colour go back thousands of years, when writings of philosophers such as Democritus, Plato and Aristotle emerged (Brown et al. 2020).

Other notable theories of colour developed through the centuries in the work of significant scholars, scientists and artists such as: al-Kindi, Leonardo da Vinci, Robert Fludd, Isaac Newton, Johann Wolfgang von Goethe and others. **Leonardo da Vinci** was the first to talk about the various colour principles. **Isaac Newton** introduced a new theory of colour in 1666, in which he revealed the concept of primary colours. The entomologist **Moses Harris** was influenced by Newton's theory in creating the first colour wheel in 1766, which consisted of the primary colours. In the early 20th century, German painter **Johannes Itten** extended the previous version of the colour wheel by adding secondary and tertiary colours. He also came up with the idea of classifying warm and cool colours (Gage 2000), while Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, in his "Theory of colours", published in 1810, had introduced the idea of colour temperature linked to the psychological impact of different colours on mood and emotion.

The colour wheel invented by Newton speaks about three *primary colours* (blue, red, yellow), three *secondary colours* (green, orange, purple) and *tertiary colours* (red-orange; red-purple/violet; yellow-orange; yellow-green; Blue-green; Blue-purple/violet). The real basis for the colour wheel is rooted in Newton's experiments with prisms (Munsell n.d.)

Figure 15. Drawing thought to be Claude Boutet's seven-colour and twelve-colour colour circles; Wikimedia

Several colour schemes emerge from different colour (Arty Factory n.d.; Color Matters n.d.) While complementary and analogous are two of the well-known colour schemes, there are also split-complementary and triadic, and others like square and tetradic (<https://www.colormatters.com/color-and-design/basic-color-theory>). Complementary colours are opposite or “across” one another. For example, red and green, blue and orange, and yellow and purple. This also applies to all the tertiary colours that are also opposite/across each other. This is referred to as a colour scheme and provides contrast in a visual composition due to their opposite placements.

Another popular scheme includes analogous colours, which are adjoining colours; just like opposites can be a pair, so too can colours that are side-by-side. For example, red, red-orange, red-purple/violet, or orange, yellow-orange, red-orange, etc.

The split-complementary colour scheme applies to what is referred to as the “dominant” colour, which can be the primary or secondary colour and the two colours next to its opposite colour. If we use red as an example, the two colours that are on either side of red’s complementary colour, which is green, would be blue-green and yellow-green, respectively.

The triadic colour scheme applies colours that are an even distance from one another. There are usually three spaces between each colour. As an example, this could look like green, orange, and purple. Similarly, the combination of the primary colours will also make a triadic colour scheme.

Figure 16. Colour Mixing Guide: Proportions for mixing all known colours; Wikimedia

The German painter **Philipp Otto Runge** was the next to propose a colour wheel model. His 1807 model took Mayer’s notion of three “pure” colours, plus black-and-white, and spread these ideas over and inside a 3D colour sphere. In 1839, his model gave way to **Michel Eugène Chevreul’s** hemispherical system (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Hemispherical system of color wheel according Michel Eugene Chevreul

Chevreul arranged his 72 colours in a hemisphere, with similar proportional relationships between shades as those proposed by Mayer. The use of black and white as a lightening or darkening agent was called the “nero” factor. He also described a phenomenon known as Chevreul’s illusion: the way two identical colours of different intensities, when placed adjacent to each other, seem brighter at the edge where they join.

In 1900, **Albert Henry Munsell’s** cylindrical system (see Figure 18), brought colour theory into the 20th century with an appropriately futuristic visual model (Ohta and Robertson, 2005). Munsell opted for a three-dimensional cylinder, in which the three axes showed *hue*, *value* (lightness or darkness), and *chroma* (colour purity). In quantifying colour using these three values, this model

described colours more scientifically than previous models, which themselves cracked the colour wheel concept wide open in favour of more ersatz shapes: Hermann von Helmholtz's cone in 1860, William Benson's tilted cube in 1868, and August Kirschmann's grandiloquent sounding "slanted double-cone" from 1895.

Figure 18. Munsell colour system representation

A.H. Munsell and Newton shared the concept of likening colour notation to music notation. In his original *colour wheel* (1704), Newton included musical notes correlated with colour beginning with red and dividing the circle by the musical scale starting with D and ending with the octave of D. It was no surprise that violet and purple colours are located next to red on the wheel, since they are considered non-spectral and mixtures of red and violet light. Munsell's model and subsequent books of colour follow a similar order as Sir Isaac Newton, who represented on a wheel the colours of the visible spectrum of light - ROY G BIV (red, orange, yellow, green, blue, indigo and violet) (Munsell n.d.).

A few other models have emerged since Munsell – notably CIELAB and CIECAM2 – but Munsell's system is still used in different fields where colour is important (identification of skin and hair colours for forensic pathology, for matching soil colours, in prosthodontics for selecting tooth shades for dental restorations, and for matching beer colours).

Artists like **Piet Mondrian** utilized primary colours in abstract paintings, such as *Composition with Red, Blue, and Yellow* (1930). An example of complementary use of colours in art is **Vincent van Gogh's** *The Night Café* (1888), where the red of the walls complements the green of the ceiling. Van Gogh was indeed popular for utilizing different colour schemes in his paintings. Another example of translation of these colour theories in art is from **Mark Rothko's** Colour Field paintings like *Orange, Red, and Yellow* (1961), where we can see large areas of orange and a band of yellow at the top of the composition with a red background.

Colour value refers to the level of light or darkness of a colour. It is determined when looking at a black and white image. This can also be viewed on what is referred to as a gradient or a grayscale, which will show how colours go from lighter to darker, namely from white to black, including the transitional colours in between. A low-key colour value means it is darker and created when more

black is added to a colour; a high-key colour value means it is lighter and created when whiter is added to a colour. Colour value in visual arts is important because it is what creates the effect of depth or three-dimensionality (Arty Factory n.d.).

The intensity in colour is also usually referred to as *saturation* or *chroma*. This is commonly described as the “brightness or dullness” of a colour. When a colour is unmixed it is known as being in its “pure” or more brilliant form (Lewis 2022).

Colour intensity can be applied when it is needed to create spatial depth or draw attention to a focal point. An example of colour in art that utilizes a high level of colour saturation can be seen in **Ernst Ludwig Kirchner’s** *Seated Girl (Fränzi Fehrmann)* (1910). In **Claude Monet’s** *Impression, Sunrise* (1872), there is a lower colour saturation, however, higher intensity is evident in the sun, which becomes the focal point of the composition.

The *colour temperature* refers to some colours like reds or yellows that appear warmer and others like blue or green that appear cooler. As example of warm colours we can consider the yellows in **Vincent van Gogh’s** “*Sunflowers*” (1888), while for cold or cooler colours we can choose **Claude Monet’s** “*Water Lilies*” (1906) housed at the Art Institute of Chicago (AIC).

Colour has always been recognized for its *symbolic power* (Birren 2006; Anderson Feisner and Reed 2016). Our understanding and interpretation of colour symbolism has changed over time and varies from culture to country.

Red through its association with fire and blood is used to represent danger, anger and violence but also passion, love and sacredness. In **Paul Gauguin’s** *Vision after the Sermon*, Jacob wrestles with the angel in a blood red field of spiritual battle, a metaphor for his internal struggle against the will of God.

Orange symbolizes creativity, change, energy and endurance and also Autumn energy. As a secondary colour it combines elements of the colours used to mix it: the creative passion of red with the energy and joy of yellow (Arty Factory n.d.). **Mark Rothko** encouraged viewers to stand close to his large paintings so that they became spiritually immersed in the experience of colour. His painting *Orange and Yellow* is the door to an inferno of colour with a radiant energy that invites the spectator to open their emotions to “a spiritual kinship with primitive and archaic art”.

Yellow is the colour of the sun and power, being related to symbolism of life, energy, happiness, hope and wisdom. **Vincent van Gogh’s** *Sunflowers* is painted almost entirely with yellow and without any shadows, expressing the radiance of sunshine rather than giving us a detailed description of what the flowers look like. Van Gogh also uses yellow as the symbol of hope, gratitude and friendship as the *Sunflowers* series was painted to welcome his friend Paul Gauguin to the Yellow House in Arles.

Green is the colour of grass and trees and all that is associated with nature, health and growth. However, it is also used to represent more negative traits such as envy and inexperience. **Cézannes** painting of *The Bridge at Maincy* (1879, oil on canvas) is a formal composition of horizontal, vertical and diagonal lines whose rigor is somewhat relieved by the curves of the bridge. Paul Cézanne called his paintings, “constructions after nature”, as he saw painting in abstract terms as the construction and arrangement of colour on a two-dimensional surface. The composition was simply a vehicle to assist with the realization of this surface structure of pattern and colour.

Blue is the coolest and most calming of all the colours, representing the sky, heavens but also deep waters of seas and oceans. In classical mythology, blue was the colour associated with the gods, Venus and Jupiter. In Christianity, it becomes the symbol of the Virgin Mary as Queen of Heaven. The calmness of blue is seldom more visible than in the **Whistler’s** *Nocturne, Blue and Silver: Chelsea* (1871, oil on wood) representing a view at twilight from Battersea looking across to Chelsea.

The style is strongly influenced by the Japanese art of ‘ukiyo-e’ which translates as ‘pictures of the floating world’.

Purple is the colour of royalty, wealth and power as only rich people could afford to wear clothes of this luxurious colour (mainly made from rare and expensive dyes). Catherine II, known as Catherine the Great, supported the development of the arts, literature and education in Russia. She is portrayed by **Fyodor Rokotov** wearing a gown of the finest purple silk draped with ermine robes, clothes worthy of her noble status in *Catherine the Great* (1780).

Brown is the colour of earth, wood and stone, evoking craftsmanship and the connection with earth and mud. It is also used to represent humility: a down-to-earth virtue. **Vincent Van Gogh** painted “*Shoes*” (1888, oil on canvas) by using a darker palette of his earlier work to reflect the humility of the subject matter. Van Gogh paints the shoes of a humble peasant in rugged earthy browns to suggest the hardship of their owner’s life and to pay respect to the dignity of manual labour (Arty Factory n.d.)

Black and its association with darkness and heavy emotions or feelings is used to represent death, evil, witchcraft, fear and mourning. *The Widow* (1922-23, woodcut) by **Käthe Kollwitz** is one of a series of prints from a portfolio called *Krieg* (War) which deals with the human tragedy of the first World War. This is a desolate image of a grief-stricken wife who is embracing the memory of her lost husband. Black is the only appropriate colour for such a sad and distressing subject.

Grey is the natural colour of some metals and stone, but it also has some negative associations with the weather, boredom, decay. Ashes, dust and old age. Grey is a mixture of black (death) and white (peace) and as such it is also associated with death and mourning. *Goat Skull, Bottle and Candle* (1952, oil on canvas) by **Pablo Picasso** is a modern *vanitas* still life - a traditional genre that addresses the idea of our mortality. *Vanitas* still-lives depicted objects that had a symbolic meaning: a skull as a symbol of death or a candle as the transient flame of life.

Picasso often painted in monochrome to enhance the emotional charge of his work. He is noted for his blue and rose periods as well as the unifying brown tones of analytical cubism. However, he painted in grey tones (grisaille) several works suggesting death and oppression: *Guernica* (1937), *The Charnel House* (c.1944-48), the Goya inspired *Massacre in Korea* (1951).

White and its association with light is used to represent peace, purity, cleanliness, innocence, hope and goodness. In 1915, the Russian artist **Kazimir Malevich** developed a geometric style of abstract art which he called *Suprematism* (*Suprematist Composition: White on White*, 1918, oil on canvas). He believed that pure abstract form had a spiritual power with an ability to open the mind to ‘the supremacy of pure feeling’ and there was no purer colour for that purpose than white.

Each combination of colour can have a specific meaning from a psychological point of view, suggesting emotions and sensible state of the person observing and perceiving the colour in an art object (Birren 2006). For example, using a lot of blue in an artwork might suggest an intention to create a feeling of calmness or serenity. On the other hand, if a lot of red is used, the intention might be to create a sense of excitement or passion.

Since prehistoric times humans started exploring the effect colour has on them, and although colour was used as an attempt to heal illness at first, it paved the way for what we recognize today as *colour psychology* (as part of *colour theory* also).

In the 20th century, **Carl Jung** started to study how colours affected human emotions. He hoped to be able to use colours and art to help psychotherapy patients to heal from trauma. Over time colour psychology became a well-known field of study (London Image Institute 2020) (Figure 19). Many artists, filmmakers, surface designers, and visual artists of all kinds use to create specific emotions in their artwork.

TRANQUILITY AUTHORITY WISDOM STABILITY CLEANLINESS FRESHNESS FREEDOM	LOVE EXCITEMENT WARMTH ROMANCE PASSION SPEED LUCK	HEALTH HAPPINESS FRIENDLINESS ENTHUSIASM ENERGETIC YOUTH FUN	CREATIVITY FRIENDLINESS CHEERFULNESS ENERGETIC OPTIMISM WARMTH JOY	NATURE GROWTH PROSPERITY HEALTH HOPE LUCK LIFE
COLD SADNESS DEPRESSION	RAGE BLOOD AGGRESSION	RUIN DANGER DESOLATION	ILLNESS DANGER MADNESS	ENVY POISON CORRUPTION
ROMANCE NURTURING INNOCENCE DELICATE PLAYFUL SWEET KIND	LUXURY MYSTERY SPIRITUALITY ATTRACTION FUTURE ROYALTY MAGIC	LUXURY DARKNESS SOPHISTICATION AUTHORITY ELEGANCE MYSTERY POWER	LIGHT HOLINESS CLEANLINESS SPIRITUALITY INNOCENCE PURITY HOPE	STRENGTH CALM TIMELESSNESS NEUTRALITY AUTHORITY WISDOM STABILITY
IMMATURITY DECEPTION MATERIALISM	ILLUSION DECEPTION DETACHMENT	FEAR LONELINESS HOPELESSNESS	COLD ISOLATION EMPTINESS	DULL LIFELESS ABANDONMENT

Figure 19. Colour psychology: meaning behind each colour in the visible spectrum (London Image Institute 2020)

Visual artists often use colours in subtle ways, yet strategically used to gain and create certain reactions and effects at the unconscious level. The use of light and dark colours also often represents positive and negative emotions, or the good and the bad. White or lightness symbolizes hope, purity, innocence, goodness, openness, angelic and heaven. Black or darkness symbolizes despair, pessimism, hidden, death, shadows or general negativity. Pink or pinkish shades are often used to portray sensitivity, compassion, youth, feminine, naivety, emotion and nurturing states.

In *The Pool of London* (1906, oil on canvas) **André Derain** uses the contrast between warm and cold colours to express the noise and activity of this busy dockyard. He creates the illusion of depth in the painting by using warmer colours in the foreground which gradually become cooler towards the background. This organized arrangement of colours in a landscape is called Aerial Perspective (Arty Factory n. d.).

Derain was one of a group of artists known as *Les Fauves* (the wild beasts), according a label given by a critic who was outraged by the bold colours in their art (Arty Factory n. d.). The artistic establishments of those times were offended by this wild use of colours as they respected control and restraint in the use of colour. The “Fauves” artists believed that colour had a direct link to our emotions, and they loved to use it at the highest pitch possible. The function of colour in their paintings was not to describe their subject matter, but to express the artist’s feelings about it. Their ideas paved a path in the free use of colour for future generations of artists, giving them the freedom to explore colour as a subject in its own right.

Another effective use of emotive colour is found in the paintings of **Pablo Picasso**. Between 1901 and 1904, Picasso painted in monochrome tones of blue which reflected his low psychological state. This was triggered by the death of his friend, the Spanish painter Carlos Casagemas, who shot himself because of his unrequited love for the artists’ model Germaine Pichot. This chapter of his work became known as his ‘blue period’. In *The Tragedy* (1903, oil on canvas), he uses cool blues to evoke the sadness and despair he felt for the loss of the friend, a rather heavy subject from this period.

Edvard Munch (1863-1944) wrote “I do not paint what I see but what I saw”. This statement suggests that Munch perceived his work as a product of the cumulative emotion of the mind’s eye. “Intentionally and consciously between seeing something and realizing it in paint, he passes through a mental filter from which it later emerges transformed in the intensity of the remembered moment”.

He often uses colour not for naturalistic description but to convey the authenticity of feeling. The red colour of the sky in the *Scream* is correlative of the figure's emotions: hopelessness and panic (McShine and Berman 2006).

Edvard Munch read popular manuals on the science behind colour and the powerful visual and physical effects that colour can have on us. These writings promoted that there are forces at work in the universe that impact the world around us but are imperceptible to the human eye—a notion that was very fashionable at the time, given the great public excitement over such recent scientific breakthroughs as the discovery of X-rays, electricity, magnetism, and the beginnings of quantum mechanics. These discoveries included new insights by physicists revealing how humans interpret colour, regarding the radiation spectrum and the way radiation interacts with matter and produces the effect of colours (Ohta and Roberston 2005). For example, because red has a greater wavelength and is interpreted faster by the human brain, appears more striking. Red became a key- colour for the artist, being used in many masterworks from *Vampire* (1895) to the blood-red sky of *The Scream* (1893; 1910?).

According to Jonathan Bober, curator of prints and drawings at the NGA, Munch was also familiar with popular spiritual theories propounded by Annie Besant and C.W. Leadbetter, whose influential book *Thought Forms* (1901) described individual colours as emitting different energies.

The artist primarily applied these concepts to his work for theatrical effect, conveying the emotion of his subjects and eliciting an emotional reaction from the viewer in turn. Munch created thus a radical approach to the way he depicted the world around him, in opposition to the conservative 19th-century art world (Neundorf 2017).

From an early-stage Munch also worked with new types of paint that were introduced on the market, experimenting with mixture of oil and tempera media, and even creating his own paints by mixing casein and glue or egg with powdery pigments purchased in several shops of painting materials in Oslo (Singer et al. 2010; Plahter and Topalova-Casadiago 2008). He was also fond of using crayons in addition to the more traditional painting materials, as many other artists of that time (**Renoir** and **Pissarro** preferred to use pastels due to the matt appearance of the medium, while **Manet** is said to have used pastels on canvases that were factory primed) (Sandbakken 2011-2012).

In the *Sketches* for the monumental paintings made for Aula Magna at UiO he even used the unprimed canvas as an active part of his palette (and with time the canvas yellowed and darkened due to deposition of particulate from atmosphere, pollution and other factors). Several binding media have been identified such as: gelatine (from animal glue) based and linseed oil for *The Sun* (1910-1911), walnut oil and boiled linseed oil in *The Researchers* (1925-27). The matt appearance of the paint is due to the small amount of binding media (oil) in relationship to the amount of pigments and chalk (Stein 2011-2012). Munch also used mixed techniques where oil brush strokes or even water-based colors (with organic components as glue and plant gums (gum Arabic or tragacanth) were overlapped or juxtaposed by lines of crayons (wax and oil-based drawing materials). Some of the sketches were painted on primed linen canvas, while others were executed on unprimed cotton canvases, not intended for painting purposes (Sandbakken 2011-2012; Sandbakken and Tveit 2012).

Munch was an experimentalist and not very much interested in the stability or long-term preservation of his works. Along the 60 years of artistic production, he evolved from a more classical academic style of painting to a modern expressionist and symbolist style. He is renowned for his unconventional, direct, and personal style. He used less saturated colours than those used by his contemporaries, but the low saturation colour brings a different, heavier, more charged atmosphere to art history. His main interest was to obtain matt appearance for his paintings therefore he avoided the use of varnishes or other glossy surface materials.

In his paintings, Munch was concerned with the effects of colour, and the way one's perception of a scene could change with time of day or emotional state. He wrote: "The fact is that at different times you see with different eyes. You see differently in the morning from in the evening. The way in which one sees also depends on one's mood" (Parker 2009).

In the works by Munch the colours become protagonist of his innovative studio experimentation, applied in thin and/or thick brushstroke, squeezed directly from the tube, blended with crayon lines and contours, pure, mixed or overlapped, sometimes even applied with fingers or other tools than brushes. This taste for experimentation led to severe consequences regarding the stability of paint layers and integrity of the representation (Froysaker et al. 2015). Nowadays many works present porous, powdery, de-cohesed paint layers, colour change phenomena (fading and darkening), abrasions and cracks, paint layers losses and lacunae. All these degradation forms lead to a loss of the readability of the image depicted but also to many questions related to long-term survival of these artworks. In few cases, as *Madonna* and *The Scream*, the integrity of the object has also been affected by theft (2004) and other vandalic acts (Ydstie 2008). A big halo produced by a liquid agent left a deturpated mark in the left corner of the *Scream* painting, the cardboard also being heavily damaged in this area.

The decade 1892-1902 represents the most important period of Munch's activity: in these years the artist defined his pictorial language, which is enriched with symbolistic elements and would go on to influence Expressionism. The recurring themes are love, death and existential anguish, depicted by deformed images and garish colours. In this period his iconic *Scream* was also born, emblematic of the condition of the modern man, prey to anxiety, inner loneliness and mal de vivre. That "great infinite scream" which according to Munch pervaded Nature, became the manifesto of his artwork, an expression of the lonely scream of all humanity (Neri 2021)

Munch wrote about the moment he saw the striking sunset depicted then in the *Scream* (also initially named the *Scream of nature*):

One evening I was walking along a path, the city was on one side and the fjord below. I felt tired and ill. I stopped and looked out over the fjord-the sun was setting, and the clouds turning blood red. I sensed a scream passing through nature; it seemed to me that I heard the scream. I painted this picture, painted the clouds as actual blood. The colour shrieked. This became *The Scream*.

It is obvious that Munch used colour in this painting to convey emotion and drama, the colours becoming an exacerbation of feeling supporting his idea, rather than painting realistically. There is a powerful contrast between exaggerated reds and oranges used for the sunset in the background, and the dull blues, greens, purples and greys used for everything else. The use of colour contrast in this painting works two ways: to show the intensity of the "blood red" sunset in the background and the drama of the figure on the bridge. Whilst the painting appears relatively simple, there is a clever contrast between two pairs of complementary colours: red and green, and orange and blue. This adds a subtle level of complexity and some interesting colour relationships to the painting. The "blood" red in the sky appears to be the strongest colour, which contrasts against the very weak green for the land.

The ghoulish figure was painted with sickly colours: dull yellows, blues, and purples. Dark and light accents painted over the top hint at the "screaming" expression of the figure. No attention was given by Munch to paint this figure with any sense of realism. It is likely this was a figure of Munch's own tormented mind and anguish.

Munch's approach to the union of senses and the belief that one might taste a colour or smell, a musical note, results in the visual depiction of sound and emotion. The visual music and visual poetry

are here combined in the specific aesthetics of the artist, resulting from the curved lines and the strong colors used to accentuate the oppressive general state of the character and the artwork itself. As such, *The Scream* represents a key work for the Symbolist movement as well as an important inspiration for the Expressionist movement of the early 20th century. As Munch wrote it in his notebook “it is not the chair which is to be painted but what the human being has felt in relation to it”. Through this artwork, Munch sought to express internal emotions through external forms and thereby provide a visual image for a universal human experience (Oltean n.d.)

Pettersen’s late research (Pettersen 2022) shows that there are several theories about how and why the Scream motif developed further and she brings up new aspects that can point towards the dating as being 1893 and not 1910?. She studies not only the stylistic features and the sources of the time of creation and own writings of Munch, but also suggests that further chemical analysis of *The Scream* compared with other paintings (i.e. *Anxiety, Despair, Hands*) could bring new clues regarding the dating year.

The large stylistic gap between *Sick Mood at Sunset. Despair* (1892, oil on canvas) (Figure 20) , and *The Scream* (1893, pastel and tempera on cardboard) (Figure 21), is astonishing. The motif has changed in both content and form: from a rendering in an impressionistic manner to a bold, “wild”, colourful image formed by expressive lines, with a new main figure. It is this figure which makes the biggest difference in the composition – it is no longer a man, but a bizarre creature, facing the spectator. The body is a wavy shape holding its bald head in both hands. The eye sockets are shown as circles; the mouth is depicted as an open oval, screaming. In one of the first characterisations, the figure is described as “a caricature figure in which nothing human is to be found”. There are recent theories about this transformation. Some researchers have addressed the suicide of Munch’s close friend, the actor and painter Kalle Løchen (1865–93) in the forest of the Ekeberg hill in November 1893 as a possible trigger. This theory is quite appealing, considering the huge difference in style between *Sick Mood at Sunset. Despair* and *The Scream*. The feeling of anxiety seems to have been transformed further in an image aiming to express an incomprehensible, extreme despair. The skull-like head in *The Scream* is a clear association to death (Pettersen 2022).

Figure 20. *Sick Mood at Sunset. Despair*, 1892, oil on canvas, 92 x 67 cm, signed lower left “E. Munch 1892”, Thielska Galleriet Stockholm, Photo: Tord Lund, ©Thielska Galleriet.

Figure 21. A) *The Scream*, 1893, tempera and crayon on cardboard, 91 x 73.5 cm, signed lower left “E Munch 1893”, Nasjonalmuseet Oslo, Photo: Børre Høstland, ©Nasjonalmuseet; B) *The Scream*, 1910(?), tempera and oil on cardboard, 83.5 x 66 cm, Munchmuseet Oslo, MM.

The dating 1893 for the version housed at MUNCH was provided in publications and exhibitions, with or without a question mark, until 2008, and there was a heated debate on the dating on several occasions over many years. Different years of creation of MM’s version have been proposed, including 1906, 1915–18 as well as years between 1906 and 1918. No certain proof has been offered that excludes the possibility of both paintings having been created at the same time. It is not the purpose of this article to address the different dating theories, but some of the points in question will be presented. The dating debate was summarized in 2013 in a comprehensive publication on *The Scream* by Poul Erik Tøjner and Bjarne Riiser Gundersen (Pettersen 2022).

The recent dating, 1910 with a question mark, comes from Gerd Woll’s catalogue raisonné published in English in 2009, *Edvard Munch. Complete Paintings (CR)*. There, one of the main arguments is that Olaf Schou purchased NM’s version of *The Scream* in 1910 and immediately donated it to the National Gallery in Oslo, which had long wished to acquire the painting. The assumption is that Munch could have painted a new version on this occasion, as he sometimes did when selling his paintings (Pettersen 2022).

In 1893, Munch rented two exhibition rooms on the second floor at 19 Unter den Linden in Berlin. Here *The Scream* was exhibited for the first time. In the catalogue, six of the 25 paintings were listed under the heading *Die Liebe*. *The Scream* was one of them, entitled *Verzweiflung (Despair)*. A couple of newspaper reviews mention the painting. The first one was published in *Berliner Tageblatt*: “but the last picture: *Despair* has a caricature figure in which nothing human is to be found; the background, a white mixture of the brightest red, green, and yellow brushstrokes: What that means, if it isn’t himself – heaven knows!”¹ (Pettersen 2022). The second review was published in the Norwegian *Morgenbladet* (1893): “The last picture *Despair* is a pure caricature. The background is a

¹ “Das letzte Bild aber: *Verzweiflung* hat eine Karrikaturfigur, an der nicht Menschliches mehr zu entdecken ist; der Hintergrund, ein weißes Gemisch von grellsten rothen, grünen und gelben Pinselstrichen: was das bedeutet, das weiß der Himmel, wenn er das nicht selbst sein sollte!”

strange egg yellow, bright red and green sky, and the figure, a small man with long hair and convulsively open mouth, impossible to understand”.²

Both these reviews mention three colours: red, green and yellow. There is a large area of green in the background to the right, under the red and yellow sky, in MUNCH’s version of *The Scream* (Fig. B). In NM’s version, there is very little green colour to be seen. Only a few green lines are drawn in crayon on the right, and some green brushstrokes run along part of the painted red vertical area (Fig. A). One wonders which of the two versions is described above – is it really National Museum’s version? It is difficult to believe that its colours could have been described as red, green and yellow. The colour descriptions in these reviews undoubtedly suit MUNCH’s version better.

In Stanislaw Przybyszewski’s article *Psychischer Naturalismus* (Przybyszewski 1894), the colours of *The Scream* are described as follows:

... Endlich das letzte bild: “Die Verzweiflung”. Auf einer Brücke, oder so etwas Aenlichem, est ist ja auch vollständig gleichgiltig, was er darstellt – steht ein Fabeltier mit weit aufgesperrtem Rachen. ... Jeder Schmerz ein blutroter Fleck; jedes langgedehnte Schmerzgeheul ein Gurt blauer, grüner, gelber Flecke; unausgeglichen, brutal neben einander, wie etwa die kochenden Elemente werdender Welten in wilden Gestaltungsbrünsten. ...

Finally, the last picture: *Despair*. On a bridge, or something similar, it doesn’t really matter what it represents – stands a mythical animal with its mouth wide open. [...] Each pain a blood red stain; each long-awaited scream of pain a belt of blue, green, yellow stains; unbalanced, brutal next to each other, like the boiling elements of developing worlds in wild creative fervours.

Przybyszewski mentions not only red, yellow and green, but also the blue colour, which is present in both paintings (Pettersen 2022).

The paintings of Munch have a provocative character given by the use of certain materials and developments in his experimental techniques of preparing and applying the paint. His subject matter was marked by unmotivated blotches, scratches, scrapes, dripping paint and areas of unpainted canvas. From 1886 onward, Munch was the most modern of contemporary Norwegian artists, due to his ability to transcend the boundaries of common convention and practice, even with regard to the most radical of expressions to be found in Realism and Impressionism (Storm Bjerke 2007).

In connection to the Christiania exhibition of 1892 Munch’s use of colour was described in the following manner (Storm Bjerke 2007):

hideous, pale colors, as blotted and thin as the first layer of paint on a house wall, anemic colors like tuberculosis patients that have never known nourishment of blood or daylight or – at their worst – piercing yellow patches, hectic reds, and screaming blotches spread aimlessly and with no apparent meaning over the canvas... On top of that, he smears the canvas with lemony yellow and glowing reds, as if he had daubed it with bloody fingers – and calls it evening mood!

In the manifest *Cosmos. The New Sublimity in Art* written in 1893 by Carl Gustaf Uddgren and Max Dauthendey Munch is deemed the contemporary artist who had made the most progress in reproducing “the intimacy of colour”: “For him, the main objective is to conserve the most sublime feelings of pleasure or displeasure that colours trigger in his brain. It is irrelevant to him what scene or event he depicts”. Munch conveys a “main mood” through his use of color!” (Storm Bjerke 2007).

Przybyszewski describes the Munch style in *Psychic Naturalism* (Przybyszewski 1894) saying about the shaping of landscape in *Despair*: “His landscape is the absolute correlation of such naked feeling; every single vibration of nerves, which have been directly exposed to the utmost ecstasy of

² “Den rene karrikatur er det sidste billede “Fortvivelse”. Baggrunden er en forunderlig æggegul, høirød og grøn Himmel, og Figuren, en liden Mandsling med langt Haar og krampagtig aaben Mund, er det umulig at blive klog paa”.

pain, is instantly converted into an appropriate sensation of colour”. Przybyszewski contends that Munch’s painting introduces something new in comparison to contemporary symbolism by using colour to couple spiritual life with pictorial expression.

Colour is Munch’s most essential tool and in colours he sees “mourning and screams rumination and wilting” (Storm Bjerke 2007).

1.4 Colours in Textiles

Brenda Doherty (CNR SCITEC), Raquel Santos (Centre for Humanities - NOVA University of Lisbon)

Throughout human history, colour has played an important role also in historical textiles. To trace the origins of textile dyeing, one must delve into the earliest history of mankind. Initially, clothing was fashioned from animal hides, but with the development of spinning and weaving, the art of dyeing textile fibres came closer to realization.

The techniques of spinning, weaving, and dyeing likely emerged concurrently among various cultures, and the knowledge of these practices spread from one civilization to another (de Graaff, 2004). It was through this dissemination of knowledge that the art of dyeing textiles evolved and flourished, leaving a rich legacy of vibrant colours that continue to captivate us in the modern age. The availability of certain pigments and dyes also affected the rarity and cost of particular colours, making them exclusive to the privileged classes such as the elite, royalty or religious orders (Cardon 2007; Mussak and Bechtold 2009).

Based on origin, **natural colourants can be classified as organic and inorganic**, inorganic are pigments while organic colourants can be further grouped as dyes and pigments. Historical dyers since antiquity would expertly use natural resources such as parts of plants (leaves, root, bark, wood, seed, flower), minerals (ochres, carbonates), insects (cochineal, lac dye) and their mixtures to create various hues.

Colours often held deep cultural meanings and symbolism where different cultures associated specific colours with values and traditions. Colours were much more than just aesthetic choices; they were **expressions of identity, beliefs, and social norms** of their time. The diverse palette of colours used in these creations conveyed rich narratives about the people and societies that embraced them, offering a captivating window into the rich heritage of human history and culture. Tapestries and dress collections bore witness to the profound cultural meanings and symbolism attached to colours. These vivid expressions of identity, beliefs, and social norms showcased the diverse values and traditions of different cultures. Beyond being mere aesthetic choices, the colours woven into these tapestries and draped across garments conveyed intricate narratives about the people and societies that cherished them.

Studying historical textiles and use of colours offers valuable insights into the mindset and values of people from different periods and societies. The importance of colour in textile collections cannot be overemphasized, as it plays a central role in shaping the overall impact and significance of these collections. **Colour is one of the primary factors that catch the viewer's eye by creating an immediate visual impact.** The use of vibrant and well-coordinated colours enhances the attractiveness of a collection, making it more **engaging and memorable**. Colours can be used to convey specific themes, moods, or concepts in textile collections. Whether it's a historical period, cultural representation, or a specific artistic vision, colours help to communicate and reinforce the intended message. Different **colours can also accentuate various design elements in textiles**, such as patterns, embroidery, and textures. The right colour choices can draw attention to these details and enhance the overall design. For historical collections, understanding the original colours and their

significance is crucial for preservation and restoration purposes. Accurately reproducing faded colours can provide a more authentic representation of historical garments.

The problem of **fading** in dress collections is a significant concern for museums, collectors, and those responsible for maintaining and displaying historical garments and textiles. It is a complex issue that requires careful attention and proactive conservation strategies to ensure the long-term preservation of historical textiles and garments for future generations. The fading of colours refers to the gradual loss or alteration over time, resulting in a less vibrant and often discoloured appearance. Several factors can contribute to fading such as exposure to light, particularly ultraviolet radiation (UV) from natural and artificial sources where prolonged exposure can break down the chemical bonds in dyes and pigments, leading to degradation and colour loss. Fluctuations of environmental conditions, namely, temperature, humidity, and air pollution can also affect fading and deterioration processes. The lightfastness and stability of dyes and pigments, and the use of certain textiles can significantly impact their susceptibility to fading due to their inherent chemical and physical properties. Considerations regarding previous exposure to harsh environmental conditions or improper storage and handling practices can exacerbate fading and accelerate colour loss. Nowadays museums are increasingly sensitive to the issues of fading and implement tailored strategies such as **light control and environmental monitoring** in display, storage and exhibition spaces as well as garment rotation and use of conservation grade materials for storage to help minimize fading (Robinson and Pardoe 2000).

Analysing and reconstructing original colours in textiles can be a challenging process. Various approaches and techniques are used through multidisciplinary collaborations between scientists, historians, and conservators to uncover and reproduce the original colours of historical textiles (Colombini 2007, Joosten 2006, Doherty 2021). Studies of historical documents that depict similar textiles or garments from the same period can offer valuable clues about the original colours. Through visual examinations of the textile, areas of preserved pigments or dyes can be observed, and any patterns or motifs that may provide clues about the original colours may be identified. The fine details of the textile's surface and structure, including the distribution of colourants and any degradation or fading patterns can be revealed on microscopic examinations (Zippel 2004). The analysis of dyes in fragile materials such as textiles, requires a continuous development of new analytical approaches that reduce the physical impact of analysis on the material under study whilst ensuring that maximum information is gained. Emphasis is given to the need for reliable, efficient, and ideally minimally or non-invasive analytical approaches for historical dye analysis (Gulmini 2013). In recent years, capturing images of a textile under different wavelengths of light, such as ultraviolet, visible, and infrared with multispectral and hyperspectral imaging techniques have been shown to reveal hidden features and faded colours not visible to the naked eye (Rezic 2022). Non-invasive portable spectroscopic techniques (UV-Visible, fibre optic reflectance (FORS) Infrared and Raman spectroscopy) and colourimetry can help analyse the electronic and molecular composition and colour quantification of original textiles in-situ and assist in identifying the presence of specific dyes or pigments (Dyer et al. 2018). They can collectively provide insights into the original colourants used leading to a deeper understanding of fading mechanisms. Non-invasive methods are often used to guide object sampling should ulterior destructive chromatographic (HPLC) or spectrometric analyses (MS) be required for identification of complex dyes mixtures and associated degradation products (Degano 2009). In PERCEIVE we construct experiments with historical recipes and traditional extraction and dyeing methods to recreate the colours observed in textiles by preparing a set of mock samples. This process involves using natural materials and conventional dyeing techniques often with the use of mordants to match the original colours as closely as possible. Artificial ageing of such ad-hoc laboratory samples can provide information on fading and degradation with close monitoring of alterations arising from modifications to the physical and chemical properties of the dyes and textiles.

It is essential to note that reconstructing original colours is not always feasible, especially if a textile has undergone significant fading or deterioration over time. Moreover, employing such analytical approaches can help uncover valuable information about historical textiles and contribute to a deeper understanding of our cultural heritage.

The work to be achieved in PERCEIVE is to supplement the laboratory and on-site methods with colour reconstruction techniques to restore and enhance digital colour information, to fill in missing or damaged areas in an image by estimating the pixel values based on the surrounding regions. Such techniques are particularly useful in chosen cases where colour data has been lost or degraded and aims to improve the overall quality and realism of images by filling. Colour reconstruction techniques could include interpolation, demosaicing or colourization by estimation of missing colour values based on surrounding known colour values; reconstruction of full-colour images from images captured with colour filter arrays; or prediction of plausible colour information based on the input grayscale data. Such methods do not always produce the most accurate results, especially in regions of complex colour variations but can be assessed accordingly (Park 2016, Lukac 2018).

Artificial intelligence (AI) can be also utilized in combination for restoring faded textiles to their original or enhanced appearance. AI can assist in the analysis of multi-spectral imaging data for faded textiles to provide additional insights into the original colours, patterns and textures of the textiles. AI-based techniques can also help in reviving faded textiles or historical tapestries that suffer from colour degradation due to aforementioned ageing, exposure to light, and environmental factors (Karthikeyan 2010). AI can be applied to faded textiles through image restoration techniques, often based on deep learning models to reconstruct missing or degraded colours by learning from large datasets of well-preserved textile images such as those from specific experimental mock sets constructed in the laboratory. AI algorithms can estimate the original colours of faded textiles by analysing the remaining colour information and comparing it with known colour patterns from similar textiles or historical references as those case studies to be analysed in-situ. Deep learning models can be trained to predict plausible colour values for each pixel based on surrounding context and patterns where AI can be used to recognize and reconstruct faded patterns in textiles. By training machine learning models on patterns from well-preserved textiles, the AI can identify and recreate the original patterns in faded textiles. By artificially simulating fading and aging effects on digital textile images, in comparison with real laboratory studies AI can create larger datasets, which can be used to train models for colour reconstruction and restoration (Pereira 2022).

This entire process from the laboratory to in-situ analysis in PERCEIVE can permit for targeted colour reconstruction and restoration of the faded areas of the chosen textile case studies, minimizing the risk of applying corrections to the original areas. Combining AI with traditional analytical conservation methods can lead to more effective and responsible restoration practices for faded textiles whilst enhancing the experience of museum visitors.

1.5 Colours in Historical Coloured Photographic Collections

Giorgio Trumpy (NTNU), Catlin Langford (Centre for Contemporary Photography, Melbourne)

One of the research domains within the PERCEIVE project involves leveraging photographs to elevate historical, artistic, and cultural moments to their utmost significance.

To explore this research domain, two scenarios were chosen for investigation: Autochrome and lenticular Kodacolor.

1.5.1 Autochrome

The Autochrome is considered the first commercially successful colour photography process. Released in 1907, the process was developed by the French Lumière brothers, patented in 1903. The process comprises a glass plate, on top of which sits a colour filter made of microscopic starch granules dyed red, green and blue and a panchromatic silver gelatine emulsion (Figure 22). In the early twentieth century, the colour process was lauded for its faithful and natural production of colour (Pénichon 2013).

Today, Autochromes are held in a range of museum collections internationally, including the Victoria and Albert Museum, London. However, they pose a number of conservation considerations. Autochromes are highly light sensitive, and the colours are prone to fading. In addition, autochromes can be damaged by a range of external factors, including humidity and moisture, which can cause greening, discolouration and silvering.

Figure 22. Left: F. A. Paneth, *Sils: Eva and Heinz at Muotathal in the Engadine, 1927*; an example of Autochrome from the V&A Museum's collection, London. Right: The layered structure of the Autochrome (Nejc Urankar 2020).

The Autochrome plate's image consists of two primary overlapping components: a uniform colour mosaic pattern and a silver-based emulsion containing the photographic image. With the passage of time, Autochrome plates are susceptible to dye fading, which is a common form of degradation that affects them (Lavédrine et al. 2013).

We are envisioning a virtual restoration approach that adopts spectral imaging techniques (Barker et al. 2023; Cucci et al. 2023) to separate the information corresponding to the two overlapping elements of the Autochrome plates. Once the optical properties of the colour dyes have been separated from the photographic image, their original concentration can be selectively restored before being recombined.

The virtual restoration can be presented in a tactile experience with a set of layers representing the photographic image and the colour dyes, where the latter can be replaced from one representing the current state to one representing the restored version.

Another type of degradation that can affect Autochrome plates is represented by the loss of image content due to the detachment of the photographic emulsion from the glass support. Here, we believe that since the photograph is incomplete and there is a public interest to see a possible complete rendition of it, inpainting techniques can be used to generate the missing parts (a description of inpainting techniques is included in Section 4.3).

1.5.2 Kodacolor

Some of the first home movies shot in colour used a 16mm lenticular film produced by Kodak from 1928 to the late 1930s. This very special film stock called Kodacolor is embossed with an array of hundreds of vertical cylindrical lenses that allowed recording colour scenes on a black-and-white panchromatic silver emulsion. A considerable amount of surviving lenticular films is today hidden. As a matter of fact, lenticular film appears like a ‘normal’ black-and-white film at a first quick look, so many lenticular films have most likely been misclassified by collectors who will need further training to identify them correctly. It is therefore important to revive awareness of the lenticular colour processes thus making these precious historical colour movies available again to a public and securing them for posterity.

Figure 23. The digital colour reconstruction process for a tiny fraction of a lenticular image – A: The input black-and-white image.

There are multiple possible methods to extract the colour information from the film images. Scanning the silver emulsion in high-resolution and letting a software extract the encoded colour information represents a modern, efficient method to obtain digital colour images from these historical motion pictures (see Figure 23). In this context, a new approach based on artificial intelligence has demonstrated to be more efficient for the localization of the lenticular screen than other previous methods (D’Aronco et al. 2023).

The results of the state-of-the-art solutions for the colour reconstruction of lenticular film is good. However, some improvements are still necessary. PERCEIVE aims to remove the residual artefacts by improving the quality and dimension of the labelled database, including lenticule warping/curvatures in the data augmentation, treating data as video sequences instead of individual frames, designing a “feedback loop” for data labelling using IQ metrics.

1.6 Colours in Digital Artworks

Arthur Clay (HSLU)

Colour is also an important part of Digital Artworks created to be perceived in Augmented Reality (AR).

This study investigates the influence of colour in AR artworks, with a specific focus on **transparency**. The research delves into the interplay between transparency in an AR sculpture and its impact on other elements within the artwork. Moreover, the study examines how transparency in AR art affects the **perception of the real world**, when viewed through the transparent elements of the sculpture (Figure 24). By analysing these interactions, the research aims to unravel the transformative effects of transparency in AR art on colour aesthetics and the overall visual experience for viewers, both within the artwork and in the context of the real world.

The **perception of colour remains consistent across digital art and traditional art**. Our visual system processes colours in a similar manner whether viewing a digital artwork on a screen or a traditional artwork on a tangible surface. Light containing various wavelengths interacts with the objects or surfaces in the artwork, and the reflected or transmitted light enters our eyes. Photoreceptor cells (cones) in our eyes detect different wavelengths and transmit signals to the brain, which processes this information to create the perception of colour (Chapter 1). The underlying principles of colour perception remain consistent across both mediums.

The difference between colour in painting and digital art lies in their **creation, manipulation, presentation, and reproducibility**. Traditional painting involves manual application of physical pigments using brushes, while digital art employs digital tools and software. Traditional artists directly control colour application with techniques like layering and blending, while digital art allows for non-destructive adjustments. Traditional paintings are unique physical artworks, while digital art can be easily reproduced and shared online. Both mediums offer distinct advantages and require different skill sets for colour expression.

Figure 24. A screen shot from the work *The Coming of a New Dimension*, Arthur Clay, 2014

Transparency in digital art significantly impacts colour perception and visual aesthetics. Transparent elements enable the blending of colours, smooth transitions, depth, and dimension within the artwork. They also convey **illumination, glow, and overlay effects** that add complexity and interest. Additionally, **transparency can alter colour intensity**, softening or enhancing certain elements. AR artworks showcase the versatility and sophisticated use of transparency as a pivotal artistic element. Each artwork employs transparency in unique ways, ranging from mimicking glass textures to creating intricate patterns through overlapping virtual objects. These varied applications of transparency contribute to the overall aesthetic and immersive qualities of the AR artworks, revealing the creative potential and expressive power of transparency in this evolving art form.

In conclusion, the comprehensive analysis of diverse AR artworks underscores the significance of transparency as a transformative artistic medium. The utilization of transparency offers captivating visual encounters that engage viewers, evoking contemplation and resonance. The integration of art, technology, and transparency fosters a transformative visual narrative, inviting audiences to explore new perspectives. This scholarly exploration highlights the potential of transparency in AR art, enriching the tapestry of visual storytelling and fostering appreciation for the possibilities this dynamic medium presents.

2. Perception

Cristiana Barandoni (MANN Museum), Vanessa Bonanno (CNR ISPC), Isabel Yoko Arteaga Kiyomoto (NTNU), Delfina Pandiani (UNIBO), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC)

2.1 Colour Perception in Human Vision

Yoko Arteaga (NTNU)

The mechanisms involved in human colour perception are both physiological and psychological (Gegenfurtner 2003; Shevell and Kingdom 2008). The human visual system (HVS) (Figure 25) is composed of the eyes, the connecting pathways through to the visual cortex and other parts of the brain, and responsible for colour vision.

As explained in section 1.1, human colour vision is based on the S, M, and L cones spectral sensitivity (Stockman et al. 1993). Although the HVS is defined as trichromatic, its capacity to recognise and differentiate different colours is very extensive. It has been shown that an individual with standard vision can distinguish two hues of around 5 nm spectral difference, and it can achieve a performance peak of around 2 nm at two areas of the chromatic space, specifically in the yellow and blue-green regions (Pokorny and Smith 1970). While the perception of colour by the HVS can be very sensitive, it is limited by the encoding of a whole continuous spectrum into three coordinates. When two surfaces of different material, and therefore different spectral reflectance can appear chromatically similar under one light source and chromatically divergent under another light source with a different spectral power distribution. This phenomenon is known as *illuminant metamerism*. Observer metamerism occurs when **the same material, under the same illumination is perceived as having different colour by two different observers**.

Figure 25. The human visual system (from Wikimedia Commons, Miquel Perello Nieto).

It has been observed that there is a great variability in the distribution of cones in the retina, even for non-deficient observers. These variations can happen between individuals, as well as within an individual, between left and right eye, and within the fovea. If the HVS considered these spatial differences, we would perceive colour differences constantly, even when looking directly at an object and then switching to peripheral vision, which is not the case. Therefore, the HVS is capable of

extracting properties from objects as well as abstracting itself from variations in the distribution of cones.

While the perception of colour can be generalised to standard observers, we have experienced that we do not always see the same colours. An example of this is the viral 2015 picture of #theDress (Aston and Hurlbert 2017, Brainard DH, Hurlbert AC 2015) (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Original image of a dress which people may see as blue/black or white/gold; Wikimedia

While some of us saw the dress white and gold, others saw it blue and black. This is because the HVS is constantly inferring queues from the scene and adapting (Alpern et al. 1972). These adaptations can be spatial, based on the scene and objects in the surrounding, as well as temporal, known as *chromatic adaptation* (Monnier and Shevell 2003). Chromatic adaptation (Figure 27) relies on double colour opponency:

Colour constancy refers to the ability of the visual system to compensate for changes in illumination, so that objects look the same colour even under different illuminations. Both retinal and cortical factors contribute to colour constancy. Cells in the primary visual cortex (V1) with both spatial and chromatic opponency ('double-opponent' cells) might be important in colour adaptation which significantly supports colour constancy (Gegenfurtner 2003). This is a combination of physiological and psychological factors. The visual system perceives the colour of a surface not as an absolute value (hue, saturation, and brightness) but as a combination of chromatic and luminance contrast relative to the surrounding environment of the target surface (colour induction mechanism). When comparing the target colour to the surrounding colour, the laws of colour induction apply, specifically the laws of simultaneous contrast and colour adaptation. For the perception of the scene, vision is assisted by colour adaptation, so the colour of the background becomes perceived as the prevailing illumination hue and is subtracted from the target colours.

Figure 27. The image on the top left is taken with daylight illumination. The image on the bottom right is the result of the scene on the top left image taken with an illumination with the colour of the top right image. We can still recognise each fruit and its respective colour. The apple appears red and the banana appears yellow. However, the actual reflectance of the banana, when displayed in the scene with daylight illumination at the bottom left appears green (after Fairchild 2015).

Another process which happens along the visual pathway is that of **signal compression**. Considering light aimed at an eye increases in even increments, the resulting visual signal will increase but in diminishing increments. This has been illustrated by Joseph Albers 1963, plate xx-1. For a visually uniform increment, cube-root increments of black should be used (Stevens 1961)

Colour perception can be affected by genetic modifications, causing **colour deficiency**. Colour deficient individuals present shifts in the peak of their spectral sensitivity curves. This can result in a higher overlap between the cones, causing difficulty in discriminating colours. While overlapping of spectral sensitivity curves leads to less colour discrimination, it has been shown that having an extra cone does not increase colour discrimination (Jordan et al. 2010).

Moreover, colour perception can be influenced by categorical factors. For example, the study by Berlin and Kay (1969) studied how colours would be categorised if there were only 2, 3, 4, and 5 colour terms. It has been shown that it is easier to distinguish two pairs of colours with a 10 nm difference which are at the border between categorical hues, for example blue and purple, than within a hue. However, most recent studies have found this debatable due to methodological reasons (Witzel 2019). Furthermore, studies support the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis that our perception of the world depends on language. For instance, research has shown that Russian speakers are faster at discriminating shades of blue for which they have distinct blue terms than non-Russian speakers (Winawer 2007).

The HVS is extremely efficient at perceiving and recognising different materials. However, the perceptual mechanisms that underlie this are still poorly understood. The perception of materials is generally grouped according to appearance attributes such as colour, gloss, translucency and texture (Anderson 2011; Eugène 2008).

2.2 The Perception of the Artistic Message through Colours

Delfina Pandiani (UNIBO), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC)

As anticipated before, archaeological evidence shows that even modern humans' ancestors already used a variety of pigments (Wreschner et al. 2007, de Lumley 1966, Mészáros and Vertes 1955, Dart and Beaumont 1969), some for symbolic purposes. Why did humans, from the beginning, colour an already colourful world? Paleoanthropologists believe that, while there could be many reasons, at the

core was a communication function (Tarlach 2018) and the relation we have with colour is connected to the way we survive in this world (Rosenqvist 2023).

Overall, the human vision system's goal is to seize from the continually changing information reaching the brain the most fundamental data, and there are certain kinds of knowledge, such as the colour of a surface, that can only be acquired through it (Zeki 1999). According to Zeki, the functioning of the brain, and its mechanisms of perception, are governed by an active and continuous process of seeking the essential and an effort to distinguish the eternal from the desperately ephemeral. The essential, however, is nothing other than the pre-existing (Platonic) Idea within us, which, always according to Zeki, is identified through the archive of forms and states that the brain has recorded. And does not the same happen with art, as well? Is it not from this archive that the creations of artists emerge? For this reason, to understand art perception as well as to perceive colour in art, it is essential to consider perception as an inner and holistic operation of the brain.

Additionally, the experience of colour is a subjective, relative, and unstable process. Josef Albers called colour “the most relative medium in art”, and Henry Matisse said that “seeing is already a creative operation, one that demands an effort” (Fourcade, Matisse 1972). Although they were not speaking neurologically, these statements express a neurological truth about the experience of vision. In fact, the context in which a perceived object is presented heavily affects the perception of colour (Zeki 1999). Additionally, colour perception is an unstable and contestable phenomenon shaped by social and material factors (Rose-Greenland, 2018). Colour perception, in this view, is a social experience (Pandiani, Pescarin 2022). The experience of colour is deeply grounded in cultural meaning. For anthropologist Victor Turner (1920-1983), colour use is **socially patterned**, and reflective of basic life-and-death processes and emotions (Turner 1970). Sociologist Rose-Greenland sees colour perception also as socially patterned: colour can signal adherence to gender norms, political alliances, age, religion and marital status (Paoletti 2012). Colour has long-lasting cultural meanings. Colours even affect mood, which explains the careful attention that institutions pay to principles of colour harmony in public spaces (Byrne 2003).

The cultural currency of colour allows for a conceptualization of colour as material. Rose-Greenland finds three reasons for doing so: she sees that to trade on immaterial sensations, we need to materialise them; second, she believes that **materialising colour perception** draws attention to the importance of temporality, specifically the instability of colour; finally, materialization allows for the use of analytical parameters that comprise cultural objects (Rose-Greenland 2018).

2.3. Colour Perception beyond Visual Stimuli

Vanessa Bonanno (CNR ISPC)

From the Greek *syn*, “together”, and *aisthánomai*, “perceive”, therefore “perceive together”, the term *synesthesia* refers to a sensory and perceptual phenomenon in which the senses are contaminated with each other. It is an involuntary phenomenon which, in its “pure form”, affects between 0.05% and 4% of the world's population. Synesthesia phenomena can be induced artificially, as a side effect of certain medicines or drugs (e.g., LSD). Chromesthesia, also known as sound-colour synesthesia, is based on the phenomenon in which those who experience it (less than 1 in 2000 people) *hear* colours and *see* sounds. Generally, those who experience chromesthesia also have perfect intonation or have perfect pitch, that is, by listening to a note they are able to know exactly which note it is. This is likely because they know which colour each note represents. There are several studies that address and deepen this issue, but, to date, there are few that talk about how the introduction of phenomena such as chromesthesia within interactive experiences related to cultural heritage can positively affect accessibility.

In the following section, we will add relevant studies and experiences which Relate Colour to Sound.

Sound to Colour Mapping.

In 2017, Dr. Bradley D. Meyer describes about how we can see the world in colour in relation to sound, exploring the relationship between the two and how the sound spectrum can be mapped to colours, both being waves which are measured in frequencies. The idea of how to visualise this relationship had already been described in books on neuropsychology. The author analyses “synaesthesia”, a phenomenon experienced by only 1 in 2000 people (e.g., even the well-known composer Scriabin) and there is no single definition. The author describes individuals who can “feel” colours and writes:

“they may see a specific piece of music or a chord or scale as being blue or green”

“Interestingly the colours are not necessarily uniform across those with synaesthesia that equates sound to colour: One may see D major as blue, another as green, red, or yellow”.

By mapping the association of colours “felt” by Scriabin with the circle of fifths, it is possible to notice an almost perfect gradient (Figure 28).

The author concludes the article by describing how colours are already widely used in music software (e.g., Iris, SpectraLayers, Metasynth, Audiopaint) to intuitively represent the amplitude or other characteristics of the sound wave.

Figure 28. Scriabin's circle of fifths

Soundcolourproject (SOVIS).

It is an experiment conceived by Kevin Groat and Derek Torsani with the aim of guaranteeing accessibility to music using visual attributes such as light, colour and texture, thus exploring multisensory accessibility. SOVIS (<https://soundcolourproject.com/>) can be accessed by having: a device, a microphone, an audio interface, access to the website or by installing the app. It offers different ways of “translating” sound elements into visual elements, such as chromesthesia, chakras, emotion, chromotherapy, etc.. The authors propose various applications for use, from musical performances to vocal visualisation and Chromotherapy Healing.

Play a Kandinsky.

Google Arts & Culture launched this experiment in the form of a minigame by asking the question “What if you could hear colour?” and involving several of the most famous works by Wassily Kandinsky, a well-known painter of the Bauhaus period who probably had chromesthesia, a condition that allowed him to feel his paintings, with each colour and shape connected to a sound, a volume

and an intrinsic tone. The project involves a narrative voice and simple instructions for use. All sounds are interpretations of artists who wondered what Kandinsky might have heard while he was painting some of his most famous works. At the end of the online experience, the user is given the opportunity to select which emotions gave rise to the painting he has just seen (Figure 29).

Figure 29 . Play a Kandinsky minigame by Google Art project (<https://artsandculture.google.com/experiment/sgF5ivv105ukhA>)

The Colour of Sound.

Flutopedia website has dedicated an article (2010, revised until 2016) dedicated to the nature of sound and colour and to how they are interconnected. The author describes how it is useful in many contexts including treatments for synaesthesia, music education and therapy, and meditation. Basic aspects related to sound (e.g., vowels used during vocalisations, musical intervals) can be connected to colour using pre-existing models, such as a direct relationship (e.g. tone \Rightarrow colour, where each tone has a colour, but not all colours can be mapped to a tone), or an indirect relationship, through the introduction of an intermediary with the purpose of acting as a link between the two. The author mentions the Chakra system, describing how the indirect relationship between colour and tone is affected through the correspondences, precisely, with the Chakras (Figure 30)

Figure 30. Colour-tone correspondences based on the height of the Chakras

On the other hand, the author talks about the correspondences mapped by Scriabin (see Figure 28), explaining how the composer placed similar colours on notes separated by a perfect fourth and a perfect fifth. At the end of the article, it is included a Clint Goss' pitch-to-colour calculator (http://flutopedia.com/sound_color.htm), which provides a visual representation in the form of colour

based on the chosen note, frequency standard used, etc. For example, choosing an A4 as Fundamental Note, the resulting colour is #ff4d00 and the calculator provides the following information:

The resonant colour of light that is 40 octaves above an A4 at a pitch reference A4=436 has a frequency of 479.39 THz. This colour has a wavelength of 625.37 nm. The equivalent RGB colours (shown above) that approximate this colour of light are #ff4d00, based on a modified version of Dan Bruton's colour approximation algorithm.

80Hz project.

This project aims to explore the image catalogue of the New South Wales State Library through sound. The idea is linking sounds to images to suggest how the latter could sound like. The authors use “data sonification”, already used in astrology and oceanography as a model for understanding large amounts of data: this allows those who do not have the ability to see the images to appreciate them in an innovative way. The project has produced an installation that has a curved wooden structure covered with anodized aluminium shingles. Inside the structure, a central mechanism displays a selection of paintings on a reel (similar to an Instagram feed).

Figure 31. The wooden structure of the 80Hz project
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vXyrvWKzMVI>)

Visitors can turn a handle to select an image and listen to its dedicated soundscape. The audio is multi-channel in order to create an immersive experience by resonating within the structure, created specifically to generate reverberations. The translation of images into sound elements took into account visual data such as: complexity, colour, tone and face detection and metadata such as date, location and subject. The compositions are computer-generated.

Jukepix (2018)

In 2018, the authors of this project faced the challenge about how to transform paintings into music and proposed a cross-modality model to transform images into multitrack music based on Deep Convolutional Generative Adversarial Network (DCGAN), and unsupervised tasks. The proposed model is trained on a classical music dataset and an impressionist painting dataset, and can be applied to transfer impressionist paintings into two-track classical music. Using music evaluation methods, the harmonic of the generated music can be confirmed. The studio uses the “MuseGAN” project, which allows you to generate music of a length of 4 bars starting from a random noise. The model

proposed in the Jukepix study allowed AI to establish a method of transformation between two art forms (Figure 32). In the future, the authors hope to improve their model by combining solo instrument tracks with orchestral tracks to generate concert music (Wang, Xingchao, et al. 2018).

Figure 32. Paintings and corresponding musical segments
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AURD8NN-6iQ>)

GANs N' Roses (2022).

The project aims to make art even more usable by allowing users to experience it through other senses, in their case hearing, transforming a painting into a melody. Firstly, the picture under analysis is introduced into a convolutional neural network (CNN) which can predict possible emotions (20 different ones) aroused in visitors. Secondly, databases containing melodies associated with the same categories of emotions are defined in order to create a system for subsequently translating the images. Finally, the machine learning models created by the team are able to generate new sound content (Cobo 2022, Salu GitHub). GANs-N-Roses is accessible on GitHub. <https://github.com/GANs-N-Roses>

3. Sense of Care

Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Arthur Clay (HSLU), Gabriele Fiorenza (UNIBO), Delfina Sol Martinez Pandiani (UNIBO), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Manuele Veggi (UNIBO)

3.1 State of the Art

Delfina Sol Martinez Pandiani (UNIBO), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC)

What are the relational ties between humans and coloured collections, and how can we trigger caring and action?

What we observe today is a general weakness of caring attitudes towards our coloured patrimony. Conservation Science is considered more a provider of “scientific facts” than a socially valuable activity that would deserve attention and financial support by decision makers. The lack of policies protecting and valuing coloured collections demonstrates the little understanding of the social dimension behind coloured artworks (Pandiani, Pescarin, 2022).

Studies on innate biological human caring attitudes shed light on the reason why don’t normally care about coloured collections. Care theory has recognised the relationship between a caregiver and care receiver: the caregiver and receiver enter into a mutually satisfying relationship and if this relation is not satisfied, the caring fails (Noddings 2002). In the case of human-to-human relationships (a mother with her child), this is evident because the ties are strong (i.e. the child cries and the mother reacts). On the contrary, with human-to-object relations, this does not happen, since the ties are weaker.

On the other side, we all have experience of caring towards objects, with whom we have a relation (either because they remind us of someone, like as for inherited objects, or because we have spent a lot of time taking care of them).

The problem, therefore, can be solved by strengthening this relationship, overcoming the distance between the visitor and the artwork. This can be done by **increasing the understanding**, transforming the experience into something **personal**, and **finally enable citizens to spend time with and for our heritage, in collaborative experiences and with co-creation approaches**.

There are a number of factors that can influence caring and can be adopted: attachment, personification, uniqueness and peculiarities, sense of wonder, compassion, perception of fragility, and sense of justice. Noddings describes, for instance, the inherent need to do what is “right”, by using the ethics of care: empathy. Above all, studies on empathy demonstrate how it is not a genetic trait, but a trait that can change through life with a number of strategies (Bazalgette 2017, Zaki 2019).

Works in the Cultural Heritage domain have identified a specific type of empathy, named “historical empathy”, and explained it as a process of cognitive and affective engagement with historical figures (McKinney et al 2018) that can be stimulated using a “facilitated dialogue” approach, encouraging individuals to share their views and experiences, their personal beliefs, challenging them to examine factual information presented while, at the same time, considering the perspectives of others. This approach has been adopted in the project BrancacciPOV, in the creation of an “interpretation-reflection loop” during an hybrid VR collaborative and guided experience (Pescarin et al. 2023).

Caring Attitude is defined in literature as *a deliberate and action-oriented event that occurs between two actors, where one needs help and protection and the other provides whatever they need* (Chaskin and Rauner 1995).

The Sense of Care or Caring Attitude is also often connected to the concept of **Place Attachment**. This concept is defined as *a strong emotional relationship that people have with specific locations where they feel safe and at ease and want to keep those ties alive* (Hidalgo and Hernandez 2001; Low 1992).

Unfortunately we don't have specific studies on how to trigger and measure the caring attitude, therefore we have carried out a specific study (Ch.3.2.1) and an exploration based on the use of a Cultural Probe Kit, thanks to a master thesis at the University of Bologna (Ch. 3.2.1).

3.2.1 Exploring sense of care in art, videogames and XR applications

Arthur Clay (HSLU), Gabriele Fiorenza (UNIBO), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Irina Ciortan (NTNU)

This section is focused on the exploration of art, video games, and digital applications that address the subject of care, aimed at analysing how these creations trigger a sense of care in viewers, players, or users through various forms of engagement. The intention of the artist, game developer, or app creator, and the reception of the audience differ to varying degrees. The creator's intention is described as the element of care present in the art, game, or digital application, while the viewer's, player's, or user's reception defines what triggers a sense of care in them.

Based on critical analysis and interpretation of the art, video games, and digital applications, the research was undertaken to shed light on how creators connect with their audiences, evoke emotions, and foster a sense of care through their creations. The methodology involves selecting contrasting pieces of art, video games, and digital applications that explore the theme of care, with a focus on different forms of engagement: visual, emotional, interactive, intellectual, and conceptual. The study also compares definitions of "care" from standard dictionaries and the PERCEIVE Project to gain insights into the varied aspects of caring portrayed in the selected creations.

Care, as defined by standard dictionaries, *revolves around the concept of showing kindness, concern, and consideration towards others, actively supporting their well-being.*

The PERCEIVE Project's definition of care expands the concept beyond emotional consideration, describing it as an *active process of protection initiated by various factors like biological needs, ethical values, and perceived urgency.*

All acts of care require **engagement**. Art, video games, and digital applications have the unique ability to **evoke emotions, prompt introspection, and foster connections** with the subject matter or themes portrayed. When viewers, players, or users actively engage with the creations, they may experience empathy, compassion, and concern, leading to a sense of care.

Different forms of engagement were observed in the analysed art, video games, and digital applications: visual, emotional, interactive, intellectual, and conceptual. Each of these forms contributes to triggering a sense of care in the audience. While the effectiveness of engagement does not necessarily depend on the medium, the chosen medium should align with the creator's artistic intent and maximize potential engagement.

Through in-depth analysis, three examples were selected from contrasting periods and media: *The Gleaners* by Jean-Francois Millet (Figure 33), *Shelter* video game by Might and Delight (Figure 34), and *Ecce Homo* by Arthur Clay and Ingo Lie (Figure 35).

These pieces resonate with viewers, players, or users, evoking a profound sense of care and appreciation for the diverse facets of human existence.

The Gleaners portrays the care extended to the marginalized in society, depicting women collecting leftover crops, highlighting themes of empathy and concern for the less fortunate.

Figure 33. "The Gleaners", Jean-Francois Millet, 1857. Oil on canvas. Musée d'Orsay, Paris, France.

Shelter video game immerses players in the role of a mother badger protecting her cubs, evoking a strong emotional connection and nurturing instincts, fostering care for the vulnerable.

Figure 34. Tracey Emin, *Tent* (1999), Tent with appliquéd text and light

Ecce Homo challenges viewers to confront human suffering and the responsibility to care for one another, encouraging introspection and empathy.

Figure 35. Arthur Clay and Ingo Lie, *Ecce Homo*, (2017), Augmented Reality

Each example's themes of care and empathy foster a deeper understanding of the creators' intentions. The diverse examples explored in the study share the common aspect of triggering care in the audience. They explore various facets of care, including **emotional care, maternal love, mutual care, acts of compassion, and caring for the less fortunate**. Through **powerful imagery, immersive gameplay, or interactive features, these creations evoke emotions, empathy, and contemplation, fostering a sense of care and appreciation for human experiences and connections.**

Figure 36. Screen shot of trailer, *This War of Mine*, 11 bit studio, video game

Creators can craft impactful art, video games, and digital applications that foster empathy and care by following various approaches. Cultivating empathy, addressing social issues, fostering inclusivity, and utilizing interactive elements are some of the guidelines that can elicit a sense of care in the audience, as in the videogame “This war of mine” by 11bit studio (Figure 36) or in the VR immersive experience “The Key” by Celine Tricart where players are lead by the narrative to experience the **sense of loss** to reach understanding and a caring attitude toward refugees (Figure 37)

Figure 37. Screenshot of the VR experience *The Key* (<https://thekey-vr.com/>)

A sense of care might be triggered also through colour reconstruction tasks. In this sense, a good example is that of **learning-based colourization methods** where, typically, the reference datasets consisting of pairs of colour and monochrome images are obtained by digitally converting available colour images to **neutral tones**. However, if the aim is to recolour historical photographs, then we ought to be aware that several pioneering photographic techniques were prone to a loss of information and a misrepresentation of reality. For instance, the wet-plate photography collected by early European settlers in New Zealand failed to capture the tattoos of the Māori indigenous community. As a matter of fact, photographer Michael Bradley recently raised awareness about this important cultural symbol lost in the meanders of a colonization process, with his project entitled *Puaki*, where he took portraits of Māori people, with modern colour photography, as well as the old wet-plate technique. These **pairs of portraits** would represent a more caring and empathetic option for a dual colour-monochrome image dataset, towards use in colourization methods (Figure 38).

Figure 38. The early European settlers in New Zealand took monochrome wet-plate photographs of the indigenous people, where a crucial symbol for the Māori culture, the facial tattoo also known as *tā moko*, became invisible. Photographer Michael Bradley raises awareness of this collateral effect of the colonisation era, by recapturing a series of portraits of Māori people in both colour and monochrome tones

This initial work has emphasised how art, video games, and digital applications (such as XR experiences), in their various forms, hold the power to evoke a profound sense of care in individuals. The act of engaging with creative expressions enables viewers, players, or users to *connect emotionally, fostering empathy and understanding for the human experience*. By exploring themes of care, creators can produce meaningful and memorable experiences that contribute to conversations about compassion, support, and the importance of caring for oneself and others in the world.

3.2.2 Exploring the Sense of Care through Cultural Probe Kits

Gabriele Fiorenza (UNIBO)

With the aim to improve the understanding of care, an experiment was conducted in 2022. A specific Probe Kit survey was designed to gather inspirational information in order to define caring attitude more accurately and comprehend its peculiar characteristics and triggers. According to Burrows, Mitchell, and Nicolle (2015), a **Cultural Probe Kit** is a tool for idea generation that is used in the design process. The probes are boxes given to participants, containing evocative tasks and any kind of artifact (such as a maps, postcards, camera, diaries, activity notebooks), allowing them to document specific sensations, feelings, or encounters. Various qualitative techniques, including surveys, the compilation of a diary, and the reading and writing of stories, were employed in this particular use case.

Date:	DAY 1
Hours spent today at my phone: [] Nr. of taps on the screen: []	

Today I cared for SOMEONE or SOMETHING: YES / NO	
I cared for: _____ (someone/something, add a name if you like)	
I knew him/her/it before: YES / NO	
It happened when _____	
He/she/it made me feel _____	
I thought I should care because: _____	
I thought I should act/react to help/contribute, by doing: _____	
Or did I feel I was not able to act/react today, despite the sensation I should do something? : YES/NO	
Did I expect something in return?: YES/NO	
what? _____	
Today I heard about someone else who did something to take care and this made me feel: _____	

Figure 39. Layout of the diary with the questions related to analyse the caring attitude in the Cultural Probe Kit.

20 participants, belonging to the 1st year of the master program “Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge” at the University of Bologna, were involved in this exploration. They were questioned, through a diary (Figure 39) and an activity notebook, on a range of topics, including their **daily routines, attitudes toward caring** for cultural heritage, and **their thoughts on stereotypes** that may have an impact on such attitudes.

The information gained improved our knowledge of the **traits and triggers of the sense of care**.

The findings include: 1) **peculiar traits**, which are the qualitative traits that characterize the caring attitude, and 2) **triggers**, which are behaviors, acts, and circumstances that cause it to develop.

Regarding peculiar traits, we have understood how the caring attitude is greater if addressed towards **something one owns, even metaphorically**. In fact, the diary entries and responses to the essay prompt, “*Write a life episode in which you felt such an urgency to care for something, that you were encouraged to act, to do something,*” suggested that some of the objects the participants cared for metaphorically belong to them as they were **emotionally bound to them**.

Furthermore, resulting data clarify that caring attitude is solely **associated with the emotional sphere** and specifically it is related with **empathy** and the pleasant and negative feelings experienced during the caring activity. **Emotional storytelling** is another conceivably important trigger; in fact, it has the power to manipulate the activation of the sense of care through the use of a skilfully prepared tale. Moreover, from the results we have understood how developing a caring attitude towards something or someone is more likely when you **already have a personal relationship** with them (in fact, 70% of the participants claimed that they already knew the person or item they cared about when compiling the diary).

3.3 Colour-Centric Interactive Participation

Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Delfina Martinez Pandiani (UNIBO)

Recent technological advances have afforded new participatory and interactive approaches to knowledge, and as such increased the tangibility of cultural objects and ideas. Some of these approaches have allowed for the combination of cognitive, sensorial, historical, and artistic aspects into one experience. As such, the advent of new technologies has paved new avenues for tackling education about cultural artefacts, their interpretations, and their implications. This is especially true of coloured cultural artefacts. In this section, we will investigate the ways *digital technologies can be used in an interactive media participatory design perspective*.

In particular, we believe that the correct approach is through **participatory and interaction design**.

The attempt to more fully integrate the use of technology with the materiality of a heritage display is part of a wider line of debate on making the museums and their artefacts more engaging for visitors, overcoming the separation between technology and heritage holdings. Increasing interest in the physicality of the experience with cultural objects is also shown by many works in museum studies (Dann 2012, Dudley 2013) as well as the rise of public installations focused on multiple levels of engagement (Brignull, Rogers 2003; Ciolfi 2007). Petrelli et al. (2016) believe that “*the digital and the material can become components for the design of a holistic visitor experience that crosses the digital-material boundary. The challenge is in weaving the digital and the material to create seamless immersive and novel visitors’ experiences*”. There are numerous recent examples of new museological approaches that take a decidedly multi-disciplinary approach with human and ludic factors in computing, such as adding content layers on exhibitions through technology, enhancing audience immersion through digital techniques, developing virtual museums and serious games (Pescarin, Pandiani 2023), personalising hybrid museum experiences through digital gifting (Back 2018), controlling interactive exhibitions through the use of tangible smart replicas or tangible data souvenirs, and more.

Color Reconstruction and Projection (2014-2016)

In August, 2014, two thousand years after Augustus’s death, color was projected onto the original marble friezes at the Ara Pacis Museum, in Rome. The Colours of the Ara Pacis, organized by the City of Rome, consisted of light projections on both the western front of the Ara Pacis altar, with panels of Aeneas and the Lupercal, and on the eastern front, with those of Tellus, the goddess Roma and the great vegetal frieze. The project aimed to bring back to life the original colors of the monument, through a sophisticated lighting system. This project was based on projection mapping and was not interactive (Figure 6, left).

Color Reconstruction and Interaction (2016-18)

A second project by the same group, L’Ara Com’era, instead had a storytelling and interactive component. A multimedia story, the experience merged history and technology in an immersive and multisensory visit to the monument, with characters, divinities and animals coming alive in color and 3D to illustrate the origins of Rome and the family of Augustus. A Samsung Gear visor was used by visitors as an AR display (Figure 6, right).

The Revealing Flashlight (2014)

Another exemplar projects that has adopted digital technologies and natural interaction in combination with colour reconstruction was developed within the Keys to Rome exhibition (Pescarin ed. 2014), in the frame of the European project V-MUST.NET. One of the applications developed emphasising the visual dimension, “The Revealing Flashlight”, was based on AR and Natural

Interaction, and allowed visitors to use their fingers as a “torch” to explore the original colours of artefacts, projected on it (Figure 40). The Revealing Flashlight worked through the Leap motion sensor, which, when the user placed the finger in the air above the sensor, recognized the finger and the movement, transferring the data to a computer, which was connected to a projector in front of the original piece.

Figure 40. The experience with *The Revealing Flashlight* during the exhibition *Keys to Rome* (2014)

AR-tifact (2014)

Another applications developed in the same context of *Keys to Rome* was AR-tifact, an application of Augmented Reality in which an iPad worked as a “magic” window through which the visitors could see a fragment or cultural artifact and its reconstructive details, including reconstructed colors. AR-tifact used the instant AR framework developed by Fraunhofer IGD, and in order to follow the general interoperability requirement for browsers, the basic system was extended and adapted to comply with multiple browsers and HTML5 requirements.

Figure 41. *AR-tifact* AR mobile applications

Color The Temple (2015) – Chroma AR (2022)

The Metropolitan Museum of Art has also developed interactive experiences surrounding coloured reconstructions of ancient art and architecture, developing a tool that used projected light to digitally restore colour on The Temple of Dendur and it also projected animated versions of the stories depicted on the Temple. Following this first experience, the MET has developed a new AR experience for the visitors of the exhibition the Chroma, with reconstructions of ancient sculptures and introducing a new polychromous reconstruction of The Met’s Archaic-period Sphinx finial.

Alternative Texturizations and Personalization: ColourColab (2019)

In 2019 a **prototype for an interactive art installation** has been designed within the master thesis of DHDK at the University of Bologna: **ColourColab**. ColourColab is a proposed interactive installation surrounding colour and multiple classical sculptures or their copies. The experience would allow users to choose one or various polychromy visualisations of the sculptures, through the use of an online tool or an augmented reality (AR) interface (Figure 42).

Figure 42. Left: The design of the ColourColab experience, allowing users to explore colourization of multiple sculptures with a variety of palettes that the user may choose from or create. The experience is meant for museums which host sculptures, as users could

A repertoire of premade palettes would be available in the lab for users to explore and play with. Some palettes are based on scholarly research on ancient pigments. A second category of premade palettes available is based on iconic paintings, art history masterpieces, or artist commissioned work. A third type of available palettes is based on the top fabric patterns of the year and the most used colours and trends of the modern fashion world. Finally, a database of user-uploaded palettes is available for any other use to get inspiration from. Importantly, it would also be possible for the user to dynamically design their own palette, including from the colours of their own skin, body, clothes, and surroundings. ColourColab’s educational purpose in the context of museums is connected with the notion of awakening, which aims to arouse curiosity, to lead to questioning and developing the capacity to think.

3.4 Art Practices and Conservation Science Data to Elicit Care and Engagement

Manuele Veggi (UNIBO)

As seen, sense of care is a broad concept: it entails several behaviours and interacts with multiple possible cognitive goals for interactive applications. Recent studies have demonstrated how curiosity is an essential component of care, as “we are curious for things we care about” (Phillips 2015). Curiosity has been indeed defined as a quest for information to close a knowledge gap (Hidi and Renninger 2020). However, if this gap is enhanced and put into relations with high level “Concepts”, which embrace “life themes” of “high levels of intensity” and “self-related information”, interest can be elicited, which may succeed in catalysing a deeper behavioural change in the visitor (Hidi and Renninger 2020).

In turn, triggering interest towards an artwork within an interactive application may succeed in allowing the audience to live a meaningful and authentic experience. Chen and Rahman (2018) indeed showed that visitors intrinsically seek for meaning as meaning-making is proved to facilitate the understanding of what has been lived. More specifically, meaning-creation is inherently linked to the establishment of mental connections (Baumeister and Vohs 2002). This active process is also considered to stem from several needs: among these, major emphasis has been laid on the key terms of Self and the identity.

This pursuit of interest and meaning creation processes as a cognitive goal of an interactive application share with contemporary musicological approaches the emotional and psychological involvement of the visitors, who should be able to “construct their own meaning from cultural experiences” (Simon 2010). The proven effectiveness of hands-on activities in this domain paved the way to Bilda and colleagues’ study on creative engagement, i.e. the adoption of art practices at the basis of visitors’ participation: this solution entails a *transformative dialogue* between the user and the interactive systems and results in “a shift in intentions and expectations”, associable also to an actual behavioural change (Bilda et al. 2008).

To verify the possibility of implementing a similar approach to polychrome’s collections, a first caring prototype is being developed, which focuses on a peculiar asset of museum collection, i.e. conservation data. They are indeed a precious resource, enabling visitors to explore hidden details lying under the pictorial film. Nonetheless, also when exhibiting these objects, museums often rely on a monodirectional top-down approach: specific details are for instance shown to the visitor, who is now able to read in that specific fragment of data the history of the painting (the most intuitive case is compositional arrangements implemented by the painter).

Albeit it might succeed in the acquisition of limited pieces of knowledge, this approach ignores other potentially more participatory strategies to the works of art, which may elicit visitors’ sense of care and interest, as well as, eventually, catalyse collaborative processes of meaning creation. In this analysis, it has hence been trying to exploit the current research in this field to guide the design of a first UX to pursue these goals in the cultural sector. The case study has been drawn from the collection of an Associate Partner of the PERCEIVE Project, the Art Institute of Chicago (AIC) and is a masterpiece of Fauvism, an historical avant-garde who gave a prominent role to the semantic of colours: *Bathers by a River* by Matisse.

The painting, which has been thoroughly described by D’Alessandro (2019), was conceived together with *La Musique* and *La Danse* and is characterized by a difficult gestation. Physicochemical analyses (X-Ray fluorescence and cross-section photomicrographs) demonstrated in fact the presence of at least six versions: the bright, “aggressive”, typically Fauvist colours were turned in darker and paler hues, and the position of the characters and of the natural elements was radically changed. Among the most plausible justifications for this change, two are the most convincing: i.e the contact with Cubism and African art, and the historical context. In fact, the Great War might have had a serious impact on the painter’s psychological status and concerns might be reflected also in the choice for darker hues and in a more rigid and vertical position of the female figures.

Figure 43. X-radiograph of Matisse, *Bathers by a River*, after D'Alessandro (2019) © Art Institute of Chicago

The developed prototype, named *MyTISSE*, focused in particular on the X-radiography as a starting point for creative engagement, as participants are expected to draw their reinterpretations directly on an image of X-Ray scan (<https://archive.artic.edu/matisseinteractive/p0.html>). A first testing session was hence organized to prove the soundness of the initial research question on a qualitative sample of twenty-four master students, PhD candidates and young researchers of the field of digital humanities at the University of Bologna. Participants, who had no previous knowledge of the painting, were asked to read and sign an Informed Consent form and they were given a tablet and an interactive pen. The device contains the application Ibis Paint X with a preloaded image of the XRF scan and two-colour palettes, reflecting the initial (reconstructed) and the final version of the painting (see a more detailed description of the testing protocol and of the retrieved results in Veggi and Pescarin 2023). Then, they were provided a brief explanation on the history of the painting and were later asked to answer a brief summary. The data were later saved as *.csv file and processed in Python.

The huge differences in the reinterpretation show how the activity is participatory as “open to a diversity of responses” and the obtained results from the survey eventually show how through creative engagement it is possible to foster audience’s care towards the collection and impact on visitor beliefs. The survey indeed asks visitors to summarize the experience and provides a selection of relevant elements, whose salience should be assessed by the participants, re-ordering them from one to five: these tasks are aimed at detecting which aspects of the experience are perceived as more important.

Figure 44. Reinterpretation of Matisse, *Bathers by a River*, Participant C3

The results are hence consistent with the initial hypothesis: the most frequent words in the summaries are *painting*, *figure / shape* (here considered synonyms, given the context), *colour* and *interesting*. Similarly, the answers to the second question show the importance of the change of colour, the possibility to reconstruct the different versions of the painting through conservation data and the impact of the war in the composition of the *Bathers*. On the contrary, a secondary role was played by the contact with other artistic avant-gardes (e.g., Cubism) and the fact that it was conceived together with other two famous paintings.

To efficiently assess the development of caring relationships with the artifact, a fictitious scenario was provided in the survey: the artwork would be undergoing an irremediable corrupting process and, in a few years, the damages to the pictorial film may be unrepairable. Participants are asked to state how sorry they would be for this loss on a Lickert scale (values from 1 to 5). Their answers demonstrate anew the creation of an intense sense of care: all the values are either extremely high (more than a half of the participants assessed this feeling with the maximum value, 5/5) or high (more than 45% gave a score of 4/5).

The survey also invited participants to describe the major takeaways from this experience (if any): 75% indeed claimed to have received a benefit, yet a distant reading of the obtained corpus fails to provide meaningful insights. A close look, however, shows how MyTISSE succeeded in filling knowledge gaps and questioning visitors' beliefs on art, colour, and cultural experiences, as shown by the following answers:

Yes. I think it helped me to approach art in a new, different way, a way I had never thought of before. I'll probably attend exhibitions and visit museums with a different mindset from now on!! (Participant A1).

It helped me to fill the curiosity that this exercise arised (Participant A4).

It was helpful - also through the use of this questionnaire- to put down the feelings that this painting gives me, because I often do not consciously think about that when I look at pieces of art. [...] It is inspiring, thought provoking and admirable the way a painting of a casual, carefree activity such as bathing by a river, brought me a sense of sadness and fear considering the style of the painting but especially the context of the artwork. (Participant A6).

I think it did somehow. I think that it has helped me with questioning my own perception of colour and of different ideas. It certainly has me question my own idea of art and colour (Participant C2).

It helped me in developing a sense of care for art and overcoming stereotypes about styles and colours associated with an author. (Participant C4).

This enthusiasm towards this kind of activity is also mirrored by other two explicit questions, which reported a unanimous agreement: the first one concerned the possibility for museums to encourage similar activities, while the second one asked participants if they would be curious to see the reinterpretations of the other visitors. In particular, this latter result paves the way to possible pursuit of collective participation, a direction which is particularly promising to convert the cultural institution into “a social place, full of potentially interesting, challenging, enriching encounters with other people” (Simon 2010).

4. Authenticity

Federica Bonifazi (UNIBO), Vanessa Bonanno (CNR ISPC), Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Arthur Clay (HSLU), Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Samuele Spotti (CNR ISPC), Sophia Sotiropoulou (FORTH), Giorgio Trumpy (NTNU),

Authenticity is a multi-dimensional concept, that goes much beyond the realism, and that an authentic experience is the one that a user takes possession of (cognitively, emotionally and sensory), re-appropriating a virtual environment, the narrative and interactions that happen in it, transforming them from something impersonal and far, into something personal and closer to the user (Pescarin et al. 2023). In philosophy, there has always been a focus on the individual, at least in the Western world, with a distinction between the private self and the public self, dictating its connection with the society.

4.1 State of the Art on Authenticity in Literature

Samuele Spotti, Sofia Pescarin, Giuseppe Città (CNR)

In philosophy and psychology individuals have always been treated in their relations with others and the physical world, and the concept has been studied in various fields. Its origins can be traced back to the Greek philosophers. It is derived from the word *authentikós* (autós, self), and has been the subject of philosophical currents (Lacoste 2014). In philosophy, there has always been a focus on the individual, at least in the western world, with a distinction between the private self and the public self, dictating its connection with the society; self-judgement became (who am I, what is the authentic myself) crucial (Varga 2020). Until Hegel (Hegel 2002), the concepts of sincerity, honesty and moral values were used more than authenticity, linked to the potential of knowing oneself and acting accordingly, with the specific goal of being considered honest and truthful by the society. Moreover, authenticity was used to define the potential of being true to oneself for personal benefits, with no relation with the society, leading to a modern ethic of authenticity and independence (autonomy), in a continuous inner search for a balance between identity and authenticity. This explains the importance of recent studies, in the field of in psychology and social sciences, about extrovert / introvert traits: extroverts have been found to perceive authenticity more easily (Fleeson 2007; Epstein 1979; Mischel 1968; Snyder 1987).

Nevertheless, it has been also experimented that introverts asked to act extroverted (flexible behaviours) on purpose, have the same capability of perceiving an authentic experience (Fleeson 2010). In line with this, (Wilt et al. 2021) defines “Subjective Authenticity” as the judgement that one is acting in accordance with one’s true self-concept. The possibility of letting individuals express themselves, finding their meaning and reflecting, is therefore key in the development of the perception of authenticity. Furthermore, the moral characteristics and values, as already analysed by existential philosophy (Carroll 2015), seem to give importance to the meaningfulness of experiences. Particularly significant, in this direction, is the work of Jasper, psychologist and philosopher, who, in its *Psychology of the WordViews*, wrote that authenticity is what touches a person’s deeper self and endures, evolves, and changes together with the individual (Jasper 1919). He introduces the concept of depth or intensity (in contrast with superficiality), time and evolution. We can derive that an authentic experience, therefore, is something that is perceived by the individual as personal and close to the inner part of the self and meaningful; it is not the same for everybody and it may change over time and, most importantly, it can be nurtured, by soliciting the self in its complexity and in its relations.

Although the self has been always considered a reference in the definition of authenticity, and beyond the consideration of the role of society as a reference for the moral values, the inter-relations with “the others” have been even recently considered relevant and studied, such as in socio-linguistics. In this field, the concept has been analysed as referring to language, intended as a tool we have to exchange information and build and maintain interpersonal social relations with others. It is, in fact, the essence of an authentic life, which involves acting and expressing emotions in ways that are congruent with physiological sensations, beliefs and cognition (Lacoste 2014). Language is also recognised to contribute to shape concepts and to stabilise and organise knowledge acquisition (Dove 2016). According to Coupland (Coupland 2010) and Austin (1975), authenticity has a performative aspect, the “authentication”, intended as an active process that involves verbal exposition and dialogue, and as a tactic that allows individuals to establish authentic or inauthentic participation in social groups. The value of verbal exchange emerges also in the “Mediated Dialogue” approaches proposed by McKinney (McKinney et al. 2019). Although authenticity is seen today, in the *Age of Authenticity*, as a pervasive ideal, impacting social and political thinking (Varga 2020), this concept also extends beyond the self and the others. It has been used since the beginning, as to refer to something faithful to an original or “of unquestioned origin or authorship”, encompassing a process of verification (Varga 2020). This process has been recognised as having three aspects: it was considered as the action of separating “the true thing” or “original” from counterfeits and duplicates, as in the definition of “Indexical Authenticity” by Grayson (2004); as that of identifying verisimilitudes (whether or not an object conforms to an observer’s expectations about how the object should appear), as for “Iconic Authenticity” (Deighton 1989); and as a way to correctly identify “the origin, authorship or provenance of an object”, as for “Nominal Authenticity”, defined by Dutton (2003).

In addition to tourists’ expectations (Chen et al. 2018), in tourism studies emerges the relation between authenticity and realism, accuracy and objectivity (Rickly-Boyd 2012). Specifically, objectivity cannot be separated from the ability of the visitors to discern the veracity of the sights or experiences they encounter. Moreover, tourists are found to give importance to authentic material objects, when they are produced by skilled artisans, or to rituals and events, when they are associated with traditional out- growths of cultures (Wang 1999). Some contend that a sense of place can be created (Tiberghien et al. 2017). In any case, as Cohen notices when defining “Constructive Authenticity” (Cohen 1988), the authenticity of an experience is variable, negotiable, and context-dependent (Salamone 1997). In Computer Science and Human Computer Interaction, and specifically in works related to VR experiences, the main dimension considered as relevant is that of the “world”. In fact, it is frequently solely associated in general with the sense of presence and immersivity level, that involve the embodiment in a digital space (Kronqvist et al. 2016), (Loomis et al. 1999), (Stanney 1998) and with the realism of the virtual environments, that depends on the devices (Kronqvist et al. 2016). A different aspect emerges in studies about serious games, where randomness and unexpected elements are considered fundamental in the perception of authenticity (Griffiths et al. 2017).

Definition:

Authenticity in Virtual Experiences is a multi-dimensional concept (self, others, world), made of components; it works by touching the deeper self of the user, through performative actions that, through its components (reflection-emotion-sensation, exchange and embodiment), transform the unfamiliar (distant) into familiar (close).

4.2 Authenticity in Reproductions

Arthur Clay, HSLU

Authenticity refers to the ability of an artwork to touch the deeper self of a person, transforming something unknown or distant into something familiar. An authentic artwork is one that resonates with individuals on a personal level, evoking emotions and connections that go beyond the physical existence of the object.

In the reproduction of artworks, authenticity is applied by staying true to the historical context and the original artist's intentions. When recreating historical artefacts or artworks, the aim is not to produce exact replicas but to authentically represent the original artwork's essence and to show the process of restoration, so the viewer is able to see the present state of the artwork and its state at its creation. To demonstrate the above concept of authenticity when making reproduction, two artworks were taken as case studies: An Autochrome and the Alexander Mosaic.

In the case of Autochromes, which are early colour photography works, digital restoration techniques are used to revive the original colours and materials. By employing spectral imaging techniques and AI-driven reconstruction, the faded colours are restored to their intended vibrancy, thus preserving the authentic historical context and the artist's original vision.

To physically create the Autochrome for display, the restoration process involves three glass layers: the original image, the compensation image, and the target image. The first layer is a high-resolution scan of the original Autochrome, capturing its current state, including any damages, and fading that may have occurred over time. The second layer, the compensation image, is created using AI-driven algorithms that analyse the spectral data and historical knowledge to recreate the original colours and textures when it is overlaid over the original image. The third layer, the target image, is not a printed layer but a clear glass sheet that tempers the light, allowing the viewer to see the results of combining the two other layers without glare or reflection. Once printed on glass, each of the glass layers is carefully mounted in a display frame for viewing.

Figure 45. Illustration of the imaging techniques used to obtain the layers for the proposed presentation of the digital restoration of faded Autochromes.

Similarly, for the Alexander Mosaic, where missing parts need to be recreated, a meticulous process is undertaken to ensure the authenticity of the reproduction. AI methods and historical data are utilised to generate the missing portions based on the reference painting from 1831 attributed to

Philoxenus of Eretria. This historical painting provides crucial information and serves as a guide to authentically reconstruct the missing elements and honour the original artwork's essence.

The physical creation of the Alexander Mosaic reproduction involves high-resolution scans of the existing mosaic and the 1831 painting serve as the foundation, and AI-driven algorithms analyse historical data to generate missing portions. The digital print of the original and the generated parts that are missing are carefully superimposed upon one another to complete the reproduction.

The entire process of recreating the missing parts of the Alexander Mosaic is conducted with a deep sense of care and respect for the artwork's historical and cultural significance. By combining AI technology, historical research, and expert craftsmanship, the reproduction captures the essence of the original artwork and provides viewers with a profound connection to its historical context and artistic expression.

Both in the case of Autochromes and the Alexander Mosaic, the physical reproductions aim to go beyond mere replication and faithfully preserve the authenticity and cultural value of the original artworks. The use of advanced technologies and the meticulous attention to historical accuracy ensure that these reproductions offer viewers an enriched experience and a deeper understanding of the artistic heritage they represent.

The physical reproductions are complemented by the inclusion of digital companion applications, allowing viewers to explore the restoration process, historical context, and additional information about the artworks.

Overall, authenticity in the reproduction of artworks involves going beyond mere duplication to capture the spirit and essence of the original work, evoking emotional responses, and fostering a deeper appreciation for the cultural significance of the artefacts.

4.3 The concept of Authenticity Perception in VR Experiences

Sofia Pescarin (CNR ISPC), Samuele Spotti (CNR ISPC)

The three dimensions. The Self encounters, identifies, and collides with the Other (who is also a Self) in a temporal and spatial environment (the World), through a system of interactions in order to have an authentic experience (Pescarin et al. 2023). Authenticity starts therefore with the Self; it touches its deepest self and endures, develops, and changes with it. We could confirm that authenticity is characterised by three dimensions that are interconnected and that most of the components are peculiar to one of them (i.e., others-dialogue, world-atmosphere). The three dimensions are: the Self, the Other and the World.

The components.

SELF:

- Personal Disposition (Identity, Extroversion, Self- expression, Attention, Sense of Direction),
- Personal Context (Values, Meaningfulness, Choice, Goals, Challenge, Expectations),
- Cognition, Emotions, Sensations (reflection and self- monitoring, feedback),
- Personal Embodiment,
- Familiarity,
- Level (Depth-Intensity),
- Time (Personal Evolution)

OTHERS:

- Language (Exchange, Dialogue),
- Social practices (Relation, Interaction with others and Feedback, Challenge),

- Social embodiment,
- Social norms,
- Social unpredictability

WORLD:

- Verification (Validation, Realism, Reliability),
- Physical Context with its rules,
- Action (Interaction with the world, Feedback),
- Atmosphere (illumination, sound, etc),
- Time (time flow),
- Environmental embodiment,
- Comfort,
- Unpredictability and Unicity (Randomness, originality)

4.4 The Component of Authenticity of Original Colour Appearance

Irina Ciortan (NTNU), Sophia Sotiropoulou (FORTH), Giorgio Trumpy (NTNU)

In PERCEIVE, we aim to develop colour restoration approaches as an attempt to visualise the original appearance of artworks that have partially or extensively lost their original colour. Colour change can manifest in several ways (colour loss, fading, alteration, etc.) and the different cases depend on the object typology as well as on various deteriorating factors. Among these factors, light exerts the most significant impact on the colouring materials, but often its impact is aggravated due to the synergetic influence of other weathering parameters or conditions. In any case, although each of the case studies dictates a different approach towards the reconstruction of the original appearance, PERCEIVE adopts some basic concepts that are in common and refer to our aim to preserve Authenticity. Based on a set of assumptions, the restoration approaches should be guided by the artist's technique and original intention in creating the artwork, although these are seldom fully known. By nature, such restoration attempts may bring a pluralistic solution to support multiple hypotheses, but they do not match the unique appearance of the original and are thus not authentic by themselves. Nonetheless, to preserve as much as possible the authenticity of the original, which is inextricably linked to the material substance of the object, the restored renderings will build upon residual traces of the original materials, i.e., pigments, colourants (preserved or faded) identifying them as a carrier, a persistent element of authenticity. In other words, we collect scientific data about the chemical composition and ageing properties in relation to various stress-inducing factors (light, humidity, temperature, etc.) for the residual materials in the artworks, where they exist.

Depending on the type of artworks highlighted in each of the working groups, there is a different richness of residual information present. For example, in the case of textiles, the reverse side contains unfaded fibres that facilitate a restoration very close to the original (Vannucci et al. 2023; Watteeuw and Iterbeke 2018). Paintings have materials that are protected from degradation factors on the edge, under the rebate of the frame (Kirchner et al. 2018; Palomero and Soriano 2011). Although the materials under the frame might not be representative of the full pigment palette or composition of the painting, they still represent an additional piece of evidence for data collection or validation of the proposed restoration approaches. In the case of autochromes and lenticular films, the relationship with authenticity is influenced not only by the fading of the dyes, but also by the medium of reproduction, such as the projector, as shown in Figure 46. Thus, here we are dealing with a possible disconnection between the materiality of the artworks and its fruition means. As far as polychrome statues are concerned, the remaining traces might be very poor, and not even obviously localised. For

this reason, it is recommended to investigate polychrome statues with spatial imaging techniques to identify possible areas where residual material is present (Watteeuw and Iterbeke 2018).

Figure 46. The authenticity is influenced by the preservation of the original materials in the object, the reproduction media and the viewer's perception. The reproduction media is especially relevant for autochromes and lenticular films that are typically displa

In cases where residual material is not present or is faint to provide reliable information for the original appearance (e.g., complete detachments in paintings, frescoes or polychrome statues), other contextual objects or other documentary sources should be used as supporting evidence: archival records, recurrent art motifs depicted repeatedly, art history books with description of common materials, recipes, and practises typical of a certain art period. Figure 47 shows the inverse relationship between the amount of remaining original material and the level of assumptions adopted in the design and development of the colour restoration tools.

If even documentary sources are missing, then colour restoration methods relying on generative methods (inpainting, colourization, outpainting) could be employed, as long as full honesty towards the process and the level of speculation are disclosed together with the results. Inpainting is an image restoration method, where partially missing content is reconstructed based on transfer of information from the regions neighbouring the missing area, or by learning visual representations typical to a specific type of dataset (van Noord, Nanne et al. 2018). The missing content lacks information about the structure and colour, and the bigger the missing area the more challenging it is to accurately reconstruct it (Ciortan et al. 2021). Colourization is the method of adding colour to monochrome images that have integral spatial content depicted in grayscale or sepia tones. From a chromatic point of view, the level of speculation is higher for colourization than for inpainting, as there are no intact coloured areas in the original image to give useful clues. Outpainting, also known as image extrapolation, is a method that extends the limited visual field of a given image, and adds the non-captured context, by fully extrapolating the chromatic and structural information (Wang et al. 2014). Hence, the creative freedom i.e. the level of speculation (which is inverse to the level of authenticity) is the highest in the case of outpainting, when referring to the two-dimensional image domain. Nonetheless, in the object domain, when extrapolation is desired, the composition of a material and its chromatic information can be revealed from the intact content. From this point of view, outpainting is more constrained in colour terms than it is in structural terms. Figure 3 shows a graphical representation of these three image restoration tasks and the level of speculation required for achieving colour and spatial reconstruction.

Figure 47. There is an inverse relationship between the existing level of residual material (i.e., material authenticity) and the level of assumptions in the developed colour restoration approaches.

Figure 48. Inpainting, colourization and outpainting are common image restoration tasks that can be adopted for the restoration of artworks. In inpainting, completely missing content (both colour and structure) is infilled by using the cues in the surrounding area. In colourization, the structure is known, but there is no information about colour. In outpainting, both structural and colour contents are lacking for the entire surface, so this task has the highest level of speculation for an image restoration perspective. However, at the object level, the colour and composition of the underlying material can be taken from the known content

The solutions of the colour restoration approaches should be iterative, and not closed-form, as they should allow for continuous improvements and refinements of the data-driven and learning-based algorithms, as a result of updated data collection experiments and feedback from quality assessments from the stakeholders.

Another important parameter that PERCEIVE intends to integrate in these restoration approaches is Time and how Time relates to Authenticity. Although authenticity refers to the original, however, it incorporates and assimilates, and it is often fed through the entire trajectory, the history of the object. The signs of use and weathering are testimonies of the age and history, and they are proof of quality and resistance to damage (Strlič et al. 2013). The fragility of colour, in particular, and its susceptibility to change, provides evidence of authenticity.

In PERCEIVE, we build the narrative on how we can approach and reconstruct the original appearance, introducing also the time. A timeline on which we could step back and forth, and progressively regain past more complete versions of the original appearance or foreseen future additional damage. The aim of this approach remains to communicate knowledge to appreciate authenticity and share/enhance the sense of care and also manage (negotiate with) the change (back and forth in time) that is occurring in any case, (we cannot fully prevent it, maybe slow it down).

Beyond the authenticity of the material and/or the reproduction media, another important component of authenticity resides in the viewer’s perception and aesthetical preferences (see Figure 37).

5. Extending Civic Participation in Public Spaces

Federica Bonifazi (UNIBO), Vanessa Bonanno (CNR ISPC), Arthur Clay (HSLU)

5.1 The Open Museum

Arthur Clay (HSLU)

The Open Museum project, a collaborative effort between Arthur Clay and the N55 group, aims to create a portable and immersive exhibition space showcasing diverse artworks from the PERCEIVE project. This academic paper explores the innovative features of the Open Museum, focusing on its role in extending civic participation in public spaces. This text delves into the design considerations, elements, and case study components, such as the GREATWALL CLIMB and the GREATWALL PRINT, which offer visitors captivating and educational experiences. With its emphasis on safety, adaptability, and extended accessibility, the Open Museum stands as an inspiring example of fostering community engagement, inclusivity, and artistic appreciation in the face of current challenges.

The Open Museum project represents a ground-breaking initiative that seeks to redefine public engagement with art and culture. By providing a versatile and immersive space for artistic interaction, the project aims to extend civic participation in public spaces while addressing the challenges posed by the pandemic. This paper explores the key features and components of the Open Museum, focusing on the innovative GREATWALL CLIMB and the GREATWALL PRINT as case studies. The project's emphasis on safety, adaptability, and extended accessibility stands as a testament to its commitment to fostering community engagement and appreciation for art.

Figure 49. Proposed Case Study Element the GREATWALL CLIMB (right side) and GREATWALL PRINT (left side)

In terms of its design and concept, the Open Museum is a collaborative endeavour that envisions a portable and modular exhibition space, offering a unique cultural experience to the public. By collaborating with established museums, the project extends beyond traditional operating hours, providing a collaborative extension of existing institutions. The design ensures adherence to necessary health protocols, allowing visitors to explore diverse artworks safely. Modular components facilitate easy reconfiguration, accommodating social distancing and crowd management. The Open Museum sets a new standard in creating inclusive public spaces that encourage active participation in the arts.

The components which make up the structure of the open museum are the Case Study Elements, and the Chroma Elements. The Case Study Elements showcase diverse artworks and scientific aspects within a durable space frame structure. Meanwhile, the Chroma Elements explore the interplay between natural light and digital artworks, providing unique insights into AR Artworks. The integration of these elements creates a unified and coherent Open Museum Space, enriching the cultural journey for visitors.

Figure 50. A climbing hold out of cast plastics with montage details. The hold is won using a 3D printer of data from an ancient sculpture.

Two of the Case Study Elements, the GREATWALL CLIMB and GREATWALL PRINT will be used here to exemplify the intentions behind all of the Case Study Elements. The GREATWALL CLIMB introduces a tactile learning experience with ancient sculptures, offering climbers an immersive encounter with history and art. Through climbing hand-foot grips inspired by sculptures from Pompeii, visitors gain a deeper appreciation for the intricate details and craftsmanship of ancient Roman and Greek art. The mobile application expands the passive structure of the above elements and complements the experience with on the digital plane by providing additional educational content and engagement.

Conversely, the GREATWALL PRINT presents a novel approach to exhibiting frescoes affected by time and damage. The element uses transparent plates to overlay a reconstruction of restored frescoes, offering insights into the restoration process while preserving the authenticity of the original. The mobile application enhances the visitor's understanding of restoration techniques and provides a comprehensive presentation of the frescoes.

Figure 51. The Case Study Element, the GREATWALL PRINT Structure. Two lenticular prints showing the work in its present state and its (digitally) restored state. Visitors shift perspectives to step through images in sequence and experience the changes

In conclusion, the Open Museum project stands as a transformative and timely solution to foster civic participation in public spaces amid health concerns. Its adaptive design, extended accessibility, and collaboration with established museums set a new standard in promoting inclusivity, creativity, and engagement within the art and cultural community. The captivating experiences offered all the Case Study Elements showcase the potential of art to educate, inspire, and unite diverse audiences. The Open Museum's commitment to safety, cultural enrichment, and innovative practices cements its place as an inspiring beacon for the future of public spaces and artistic appreciation.

5.2 Curiosity as a Trigger to Extend Civic Participation

Federica Bonifazi (UNIBO)

Extensive researches have unveiled the multifaceted aspects of curiosity and its positive influence in contributing to learning and engagement, curiosity can be employed as an effective trigger to generate active involvement and contribution in individuals, as it can be a powerful motivator of behaviour, initiating actions directed at exploring topics and environments and always aimed at resolving some states of uncertainty and acquiring new knowledge (Arnone 2011).

Despite the numerous studies on curiosity throughout the years, a valid definition, that tends to remain as the base ground even for latest analyses, is still the one provided by Berlyne (1960) according to which curiosity occurs as “an internal state occasioned when subjective uncertainty generates a tendency to engage in exploratory behavior aimed at resolving or partially mitigating the uncertainty”. Later definitions have built upon the former, followed by multiple classifications aiming at differentiating among theories and dimensions, depending on the object of curiosity, the type of stimuli or the source of the drive. A relevant distinction occurs between *trait curiosity* (Kashdan 2004), that is strongly dependent on one's personality, and *state curiosity* (Lowenstein 1994) that is, instead, strongly connected to environmental features and is activated by specific and directed intellectual stimulation caused by unsolved questions and the opportunity to resolve them. Due to its situation-specific form and its dependency on external stimuli, *state curiosity* can arise regardless of one's innate characteristic and can be directed towards specific topics, as long as its triggers manage to produce some sort of disequilibrium or a state of arousal (Berlyne 1960). This arousal is perceived as a strong sense of urgency, a drive to act and start exploring the object that raised the curiosity and it persists usually accompanied by feelings of excitement, agitation and delight.

According to some recent studies, for curiosity to arise there needs to be a moderate knowledge of the general topic towards which curiosity is generated (Hidi and Renninger 2019), and most importantly there needs to be the acknowledgment of missing information or pieces of information regarding specific aspects of this topic. It is indeed the recognition of this so-called *knowledge gap* (Lowenstein 1994; Shin and Kim 2019) to ensure the development of a sense of curiosity that leads to start seeking for more information and improving one's knowledge to solve and fulfil the perceived gap.

The acknowledgment of the gap and the consequential curiosity-driven information-seeking behaviour can be activated through different stimuli that have been widely analysed (an overview of the different studies can be found in Grossnickle 2016), among those, the ones that better resonates with *state curiosity* are: incomplete and poorly organized information, ambiguity, incongruity and complexity that may highlight aspects of the topic that one did not understand or consider beforehand, then evolving in curiosity intended as the necessity to acquire more complete and clearer information; unexpected information as in the contrast occurring between ones predictions and expectations of how a situation, event or circumstance was supposed to evolve and what is instead, shown and proven, this trigger is usually connected to novelty and surprise and leads the individual to actively search for the reasons why this discrepancy has occurred.

Once curiosity has been triggered, the need to close the gap causes the visitor to actively start seeking for answers and improvements, this information seeking behaviour is mainly manifested through question asking and active exploration. Curiosity is resolved only once the acquisition of new knowledge to add to ones' knowledge base and closure of the precedent lack of information is completed. However, as individuals delve deeper into the topic that aroused their curiosity, not only new questions may arise, highlighting new gaps that asks to be fulfilled, but also a newly discovered personal interest develops and deepens (Hidi and Renninger 2019). This process of curiosity-driven interest leads to various forms of engagement, fostering learning and facilitating effective participation and collaboration, individuals are motivated to seek answers and explore the subject matter further. As they engage in this process of inquiry, they uncover new information and insights, which in turn fuel their curiosity even more and they become actively involved in looking for relevant resources, engaging in discussions, and seeking opportunities for learning experiences.

Through this iterative process that each time leads to resolution of some level of uncertainty, learning occurs, and as new knowledge is gained, visitors become invested. By captivating visitors in this self-rewarding loop (Murayama 2019), triggering curiosity results in a way to engage the visitors and enhance their participation, hooking their attention and evolving in an active and extended research for new knowledge.

5.3 Extending Civic Participation through Social Cohesion

Vanessa Bonanno (CNR ISPC)

A definition of social cohesion.

Social cohesion is a multifaceted and complex construct which presupposes stable and trusting relationships between different people, groups, and organizations and it defines the forces which encourage individuals to be part of and function as a joint group. Nowadays, the cohesion policy is one of the main investments of the European Union policies. It aims at strengthening economic, territorial, and social cohesion. Since the early 2000s, the Council of Europe has been engaged in the development of a strategy to promote Social Cohesion, adopting a model of society that may be increasingly capable of guaranteeing the well-being of all its members, minimizing inequalities, and avoiding marginalization (Council of Europe 2008). In the last 20 years, there has been multiple

attempts to measure, evaluate, and promote Social Cohesion in European Countries (Dragolov et al. 2016; Larsen and Boehnke 2016; Schiefer et al. 2012), and, while the research on this front is still ongoing, useful frameworks to test the presence of cohesiveness in societies have already been defined (see Fig. 43) (Dragolov et al. 2016; Fonseca et al. 2019). The most recent definition mentions social cohesion as the (Fonseca et al. 2019):

ongoing process of developing well-being, sense of belonging, and voluntary social participation of the members of society, while developing communities that tolerate and promote a multiplicity of values and cultures and granting at the same time equal rights and opportunities in society.

In recent years there has also been a growing interest in the digitisation and digital preservation of cultural heritage (i.e., the European “Horizon 2020” program) and in encouraging citizen curation for cultural objects (i.e., UK Soundmap 2011; SPICE project 2020). Thus, it is essential to understand how to enhance civic participation in public spaces in order to stimulate a general cohesiveness among citizens and cultural institutions.

Social Cohesion Dimensions

In 2011 the Bertelsmann Stiftung developed the Social Cohesion Radar as an empirical instrument for studying social interactions on national and local level (Dragolov et al. 2019). It is divided into three interconnected domains: social relations, connectedness and focus on the common good; each is subdivided into subdomains. For every subdomain, group cohesiveness indicators are identified.

Figure 52. The Social Cohesion Radar

In particular, the “Focus on the common good” domain includes the “Civic participation” subdomain, that regards the extent to which “people participate in society and political life and enter into public discussions”.

Citizen Engagement and Social Cohesion.

The European Commission describes the phenomenon of citizen engagement as “an invited form of citizen participation where public institutions invite citizens to openly discuss matters of concern and care” (European Commission 2023). At the same time, the concept of “museum” is widely

perceived as an *agora* or *forum*: “a gathering place for people and an assembly of minds and ideas – is the privileged understanding”. Accordingly, the museum institutions should ideally serve and represent the people visiting them, encouraging the establishment of new relations with the public and inspire **democratic engagement** with cultural heritage (Baggesen 2014).

The UK Soundmap project of The British Library (2010) clearly shows the citizens’ interest in voluntary participation in Cultural Heritage-related projects. The project concerns a digital collection of pieces of sounds created through *crowdsourcing*. Social media, digital technologies and the Internet are thus useful tools for citizens to access, explore and add to cultural heritage content.

In June 2023, the European Commission published a report on civic engagement, explaining how participation in cultural activities strengthens democracy and social cohesion. The report shows that those participating regularly in cultural activities are more likely to vote, volunteer and participate in community activities, projects and organizations. Because of their strong emotional, creative, expressive and collaborative nature, cultural activities can build spaces of dialogue, community gathering, sharing, social interaction and connection between individuals, features which are deeply related to the social cohesion dimensions. The report clearly states that “investing in citizens’ cultural participation is essential in any effort to promote civic engagement, democratic vitality and social cohesion in the EU.”

Cultural activities involving citizens can thus help people bridge social boundaries of ethnicity, religion, gender, age, nationality and occupational status. There is a clear correlation between enticing citizens to vote, making them develop positive social and personal attitudes, nurturing the understanding of different perspectives and facilitating conflict resolution. Citizens who are conscious of their cultural heritage are likely to feel empowered, more active in their community and to perceive a greater sense of cohesiveness.

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Annex 1

Pliny the Elder – Naturalis Historia – Book 35

[source: http://www.attalus.org/translate/pliny_hn35a.html]

- {5.} [15] The question as to **the origin of the art of painting** is uncertain and it does not belong to the plan of this work. The Egyptians declare that it was invented among themselves six thousand years ago before it passed over into Greece - which is clearly an idle assertion. As to the Greeks, some of them say it was discovered at Sicyon, others in Corinth, but all agree that it began with tracing an outline round a man's shadow and consequently that pictures were originally done in this way, but the second stage when a more elaborate method had been invented was done in a single colour and called monochrome, a method still in use at the present day. [16] Line-drawing was invented by the Egyptian Philocles or by the Corinthian Cleanthes, but it was first practised by the Corinthian Aridices and the Sicyonian Telephanes - these were at that stage not using any colour, yet already adding lines here and there to the interior of the outlines; hence it became their custom to write on the pictures the names of the persons represented. [...]
- {11.} [29] We stated what were the various single colours used by the first painters when we were discussing while on the subject of metals the pigments called **monochromes** from the class of painting for which they are used. Subsequent inventions and their authors and dates we shall specify in enumerating the artists, because a prior motive for the work now in hand is to indicate the nature of colours. Eventually **art differentiated itself, and discovered light and shade, contrast of colours heightening their effect reciprocally. Then came the final adjunct of shine, quite a different thing from light. The opposition between shine and light on the one hand and shade on the other was called contrast, while the juxtaposition of colours and their passage one into another was termed attunement.**
- {12.} [30] Some colours are sombre and some brilliant, the difference being due to the nature of the substances or to their mixture. The **brilliant colours, which the patron supplies at his own expense to the painter, are cinnabar, Armenium, dragon's blood, gold-solder, indigo, bright purple; the rest are sombre. Of the whole list some are natural colours and some artificial. Natural colours are sinopis, ruddle, Paraetonium, Melinum, Eretrian earth and orpiment; all the rest are artificial,** and first of all those which we specified among minerals, and moreover among the commoner kinds **yellow ochre, burnt lead acetate, realgar, sandyx, Syrian colour and black.**
- {13.} [31] **Sinopis** was first discovered in Pontus, and hence takes its name from the city of Sinope. It is also produced in Egypt, the Balearic Islands and Africa, but the best is what is extracted from the caverns of Lemnos and Cappadocia, the part found adhering to the rock being rated highest. The lumps of it are self-coloured, but speckled on the outside. It was employed in old times to give a glow. There are three kinds of Sinopis, the red, the faintly red and the intermediate. The price of the best is 2 denarii a pound: this is used for painting with a brush or else for colouring wood; [32] the kind imported from Africa costs 8 as-pieces a pound, and is called chick-pea colour; it is of a deeper red than the other kinds, and more useful for panels. The same price is charged for the kind called 'low toned' which is of a very dusky colour. It is employed for the lower parts of panelling; [...]
- {14.} [33] Some persons have wished to make out that Sinopis only consists in a kind of red-ochre of inferior quality, as they gave the palm to the red ochre of Lemnos. This last approximates very closely to cinnabar and it was very famous in old days, together with the island that

produces it; it used only to be sold in sealed packages, from which it got the name of 'seal red-ochre.' It is used to supply an undercoating to cinnabar and also for adulterating cinnabar [...]

- {15.} [35] Among the remaining kinds of red ochre the most useful for builders are the Egyptian and the African varieties, as they are most thoroughly absorbed by plaster. Red ochre is also found in a native state in iron mines.
- {16.} It is also manufactured by burning ochre in new earthen pots lined with clay. The more completely it is calcined in the furnaces the better its quality. All kinds of red ochre have a drying property, and consequently will be found suitable in plasters even for erysipelas.
- {17.} [36] Half a pound of sinopis from Pontus, ten pounds of bright yellow ochre and two pounds of Greek earth of Melos mixed together and pounded up for twelve successive days make 'leucophorum,' a cement used in applying gold-leaf to wood.
- {18.} Paraetionium is called after the place of that name in Egypt. It is said to be sea-foam hardened with mud, and this is why tiny shells are found in it. It also occurs in the island of Crete and in Cyrene. At Rome it is adulterated with Cimolian clay which has been boiled and thickened. The price of the best quality is 50 denarii per 6 pounds. It is the most greasy of all the white colours and makes the most tenacious for plasters because of its smoothness.
- {19.} [37] Melinum also is a white colour, the best occurring in the island of Melos. It is found in Samos also, but the Samian is not used by painters, because it is excessively greasy. It is dug up in Samos by people lying on the ground and searching for a vein among the rocks. It has the same use in medicine as earth of Eretria; it also dries the tongue by contact, and acts as a depilatory, with a cleansing effect. It costs a sesterce per pound. The third of the white pigments is ceruse or lead acetate, the nature of which we have stated in speaking of the ores of lead. There was also once a native ceruse found on the estate of Theodotus at Smyrna, which was employed in old days for painting ships. At the present time all ceruse is manufactured from lead and vinegar, as we said.
- {20.} [38] Burnt ceruse was discovered by accident, when some was burnt up in jars in a fire at Piraeus. It was first employed by Nicias above mentioned. Asiatic ceruse is now thought the best; it is also called purple ceruse and it costs 6 denarii per pound. It is also made at Rome by calcining yellow ochre which is as hard as marble and quenching it with vinegar. Burnt ceruse is indispensable for representing shadows.
- {21.} Eretrian earth is named from the country that produces it. It was employed by Nicomachus and Parrhasius. [...]
- {22.} [39] According to Juba sandarach or realgar and ochre are products of the island of Topazus in the Red Sea, but they are not imported from those parts to us. We have stated the method of making sandarach. An adulterated sandarach is also made from ceruse boiled in a furnace. It ought to be flame-coloured. Its price is 5 asses per pound.
- {23.} [40] If ceruse is mixed with red ochre in equal quantities and burnt, it produces sandyx or vermilion - though it is true that I observe Virgil held the view that sandyx is a plant, from the line [...]
- {24.} Among the artificial colours is also Syrian colour, which as we said is used as an undercoating for cinnabar and red lead. It is made by mixing sinopis and sandyx together.
- {25.} [41] Black pigment will also be classed among the artificial colours, although it is also derived from earth in two ways; it either exudes from the earth like the brine in salt pits, or actual earth

of a sulphur colour is approved for the purpose. Painters have been known to dig up charred remains from graves thus violated to supply it. All these plans are troublesome and new-fangled; for black paint can be made in a variety of ways from the soot produced by burning resin or pitch, owing to which factories have actually been built with no exit for the smoke produced by this process. The most esteemed black paint is obtained in the same way from the wood of the pitch-pine. It is adulterated by mixing it with the soot of furnaces and baths, which is used as a material for writing. [42] Some people calcine dried wine-lees, and declare that if the lees from a good wine are used this ink has the appearance of Indian ink. The very celebrated painters Polygnotus and Micon at Athens made black paint from the skins of grapes, and called it grape-lees ink. Apelles invented the method of making black from burnt ivory; the Greek name for this is elephantinon. [43] There is also an Indian black, imported from India, the composition of which I have not yet discovered. A black is also produced with dyes from the black floescence which adheres to bronze pans. One is also made by burning logs of pitch-pine and pounding the charcoal in a mortar. The cuttlefish has, a remarkable property in forming a black secretion, but no colour is made from this. The preparation of all black is completed by exposure to the sun, black for writing ink receiving an admixture of gum and black for painting walls an admixture of glue. Black pigment that has been dissolved in vinegar is difficult to wash out.

- {26.} [44] Among the remaining colours which because of their high cost, as we said, are supplied by patrons, dark purple holds the first place. It is produced by dipping silversmiths' earth along with purple cloth and in like manner, the earth absorbing the colour more quickly than the wool. The best is that which being the first formed in the boiling cauldron becomes saturated with the dyes in their primary state, and the next best produced when white earth is added to the same liquor after the first has been removed; and every time this is done the quality deteriorates, the liquid becoming more diluted at each stage. [45] The reason why the dark purple of Puteoli is more highly praised than that of Tyre or Gaetulia or Laconia, places which produce the most costly purples, is that it combines most easily with hyssinum and madder which cannot help absorbing it. The cheapest comes from Canusium. The price is from one to thirty denarii per pound. Painters using it put a coat of sandyx underneath and then add a coat of dark purple mixed with egg, and so produce the brilliance of cinnabar; if they wish instead to produce the glow of purple, they lay a coat of blue underneath, and then cover this with dark purple mixed with egg.
- {27.} [46] Of next greatest importance after this is indigo, a product of India, being a slime that adheres to the scum upon reeds. When it is sifted out it is black, but in dilution it yields a marvellous mixture of purple and blue. There is another kind of it that floats on the surface of the pans in the purple dye-shops, and this is the 'scum of purple.' People who adulterate it stain pigeons' droppings with genuine indigo, or else colour earth of Selinus or ring-earth with woad. It can be tested by means of a live coal, as if genuine it gives off a brilliant purple flame and a smell of the sea while it smokes; on this account some people think that it is collected from rocks on the coast. The price of indigo is 20 denarii per pound. Used medicinally it allays cramps and fits and dries up sores.
- {28.} [47] Armenia sends us the substance named after it, Armenian. This also is a mineral that is dyed like malachite, and the best is that which most closely approximates to that substance, the colour partaking also of dark blue. Its price used to be rated at 300 sesterces per pound. A sand has been found all over the Spanish provinces that admits of similar preparation, and accordingly the price has dropped to as low as six denarii. It differs from dark blue by a light

white glow which renders this blue colour thinner in comparison. It is only used in medicine to give nourishment to the hair, and especially the eyelashes.

- {29.} [48] There are also two colours of a very cheap class that have been recently discovered: one is the green called Appian, which counterfeits malachite; just as if there were too few spurious varieties of it already! It is made from a green earth and is valued at a sesterce per pound.
- {30.} The other colour is that called 'ring-white,' which is used to give brilliance of complexion in paintings of women. This itself also is made from white earth mixed with glass stones from the rings of the lower classes, which accounts for the name 'ring-white.'
- {31.} [49] Of all the colours those which love a dry surface of white clay, and refuse to be applied to a damp plaster, are purple, indigo, blue, Melian, orpiment, Appian and ceruse. Wax is stained with these same colours for encaustic paintings, a sort of process which cannot be applied to walls but is common for ships of the navy, and indeed nowadays also for cargo vessels, since we even decorate vehicles with paintings, so that no one need be surprised that even logs for funeral pyres are painted; and we like gladiators going into the fray to ride in splendour to the scene of their death or at all events of carnage. Thus to contemplate all these numbers and great variety of colours prompts us to marvel at former generations.
- {32.} [50] Four colours only were used by the illustrious painters Apelles, Aetion, Melanthis and Nicomachus to execute their immortal works - of whites, Melinum; of yellow ochres, Attic; of reds, Pontic Sinopis; of blacks, atramentum - although their pictures each sold for the wealth of a whole town. Nowadays when purple finds its way even on to party-walls and when India contributes the mud of her rivers and the gore of her snakes and elephants, there is no such thing as high-class painting. Everything in fact was superior in the days when resources were scantier. The reason for this is that, as we said before, it is values of material and not of genius that people are now on the lookout for.

[...]

[97] [*apelles*] His inventions in the art of painting have been useful to all other painters as well, but there was one which nobody was able to imitate: when his works were finished he used to cover them over with a black varnish of such thinness that its very presence, while its reflexion threw up the brilliance of all the colours and preserved them from dust and dirt, was only visible to anyone who looked at it close up, but also employing great calculation of lights, so that the brilliance of the colours should not offend the sight when people looked at them as if through muscovy-glass and so that the same device from a distance might invisibly give sombreness to colours that were too brilliant. [98] Contemporary with Apelles was Aristides of Thebes. He was the first of all painters who depicted the mind and expressed the feelings of a human being, what the Greeks term *ēthē*, and also the emotions; he was a little too hard in his colours.